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Abbreviations

ADME - Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion

AIC - Akaike information criterion

AO - Adverse Outcome

AOP - Adverse Outcome Pathway

BALC - Bronchoalveolar lavage cells

BALF - Bronchoalveolar lavage fluid

BH - Benjamini & Hochberg

BMD - Benchmark Dose

BMR - Benchmark Response

CV - Coefficient of Variation

CTD - Comparative Toxicogenomics Database

DE - Differential Equation

DEG - Differentially Expressed Gene

EFSA - European Food Safety Authority

ENM - Engineered Nanomaterial

GEO - Gene Expression Omnibus

GHS - Global Harmonized System

FC - Fold Change

FDR - False discovery Rate

FF - Far Field

FSLV - Final Safety Limit Values

GUI - Graphical User Interface

HMC - Hamiltonian Monte Carlo

HTTP - Hypertext Transfer Protocol

IPLD - Initial Peripheral Lung Dose

JECFA - Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives

KE - Key Event

LCIZ - Local Control Influencing Zone

LOAEL - Lowest Observed Adverse Effect Level

LOWESS - Locally WEighted Scatterplot Smoothing

MIE - Molecular Initiating Event

MOA - Mechanism-of-Action

MOE - Margins Of Exposure

MPPD - Multiple-Path Particle Dosimetry

NF - Near Field

NM - Nanomaterial

NOAEL - No Observed Adverse Effect Level

NOD – nucleotide-binding oligomerisation domain (receptors)

NP - Nanoparticle

ODE - Ordinary Differential Equation

PBPK - Physiologically - Based Pharmacokinetic

p.e. - post exposure

PC - Phagocytizing Cells

PDF - Probability Density Function

PEC - Predicted Environmental Concentration

PI - Prediction Interval

PM - Particulate Matter

POD - Points-of-Departure

PPE - Personnel Protective Equipment

PPAR – Peroxisome Proliferator-activated receptor

PSD - Particle Size Distribution

QSAR - Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship

RA - Risk Assessment

RCR - Risk Characterization Ratio

REST - Representational State Transfer

RP - Reference Points

RTM - Representative Test Material

UI - User Interface

VPC - Visual Predictive Check

WPNM - Working Party on Manufactured Nanomaterials

Summary

In deliverable D6.1, we described a number of computationally oriented tools and methodologies that can be used to simulate exposure to Engineered Nanomaterials (ENMs) and to obtain hazard predictions. In addition, a detailed risk assessment (RA) workflow was presented based on the integration of these tools which allows the user to choose among many alternative routes to arrive at the risk estimation. During the last 12 months of the project, emphasis was given to further developing the computational tools and infrastructure to the level that they can be technically integrated with the aim of creating a complete web based decision support tool for RA. To this end, the Jaqpot modelling environment was extended by developing and integrating a generic infrastructure, which allows implementation and hosting of any type of biokinetics model regardless of its complexity and simulation of the internal exposure to single or multiple doses of ENMs. A gene expression analysis workflow was developed for estimating Points of Departure (POD) in Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOP), i.e. levels of ENM concentrations in specific tissues or organs of the body that can trigger a Molecular Initiating Event (MIE) leading to an adverse outcome. The method was originally presented in Deliverable 6.2 but was further developed during the last six months to account for the additional parameter of time post exposure (p.e.). A new web application was developed and was incorporated within the Enalos cloud platform that integrates the various tools and implements and demonstrates the complete web-based decision support workflow for RA.

The current deliverable D6.3 presents all these new developments within the NanoCommons project from the point of view of creating and implementing a complete ENM risk assessment case study. The ENM of choice for the demonstration case study was 20 nm TiO₂ NMs because it is commercially available, already in use in the industrial sector and there exists data that allows us to develop and integrate all the components of the workflow, i.e. external exposure simulations produced by the GUIDEnano tool, the Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) model that estimated the distribution of TiO₂ NMs in various compartments (organs) in mice and the gene expression analysis tool, which computed PODs concerning the activation of AOP 173 (lung fibrosis). The individual models are presented separately and finally the integrated RA tool, available through the Enalos cloud platform, is demonstrated in different exposure scenarios.

The detailed presentation of the RA decision support system showcases the efficiency, utility and interconnection capabilities of the various tools available through the NanoCommons e-infrastructure. It also demonstrates that these tools can be technically integrated towards the development and implementation of complex workflows and analysis applications, which are useful for stakeholders involved in the area of ENM safety assessment. The complete documentation of the models and the approaches, including the underpinning datasets, is a critical aspect of their acceptance by users and regulators and as such is a key part of the dissemination of the models.

1. Introduction

The production of Engineered nanomaterials (ENMs) is ever increasing in both the number of substances and the volumes manufactured, and a wide variety of innovative products are continuously added to the market, making their risk assessment (RA) in terms of human health and the environment critical and challenging. Policy makers, and national and international agencies and organisations together with industry and the scientific community collaborate to ensure the safety of the public and environmental health. However, the amount and the diversity of ENM-enabled products makes the need for commonly accepted, science based, and easily updated RA tools and workflows of paramount importance. Also, with our knowledge and understanding of the adverse effects of exposure of organisms to ENMs and the modes of action by which ENMs affect organisms deepening, molecular biology-informed RA is our vision for the future. Our approach aims to provide precise and personalized risk quantification, tailored to the specific exposure conditions as well as to the characteristics of the organism exposed. This will have significant impact for both industry and regulators, serving to remove much of the current uncertainty and support the adoption of an updated evidence-based rationale for their technological and regulatory decision-making.

NanoCommons has developed a complete, unified, and structured approach for ENM RA by interconnecting a collection of tools and methodologies, developed, and offered by NanoCommons partners, through the NanoCommons e-infrastructure. The proposed methodology for successfully performing RA for ENMs is based on the conventional bulk chemicals RA, which is however expanded to account for the special features of ENM. Among these, the complex nanoscale structure, and the modifications that ENMs undergo during their life cycle which result in various distinctive toxicity patterns are particularly noteworthy. The core component of the NanoCommons ENM RA workflow aims to compare the level of exposure with the relevant hazard limit value to calculate the respective Risk Characterization Ratio (RCR). The offered suite of tools fall into three broad categories: 1) exposure level estimation, 2) hazard values databases and estimation tools and 3) combination to provide accurate and meaningful risk analysis.

The NanoCommons RA workflow as well as the combination of the individual models into a complete framework for an integrated computational workflow to enable a quantitative RA, has been described in detail in Deliverable 6.1 “A workflow and checklist for experimental design and informatics workflow for risk assessment for use in WP9”. In addition, we have also provided a checklist and a set of best practices instructions to facilitate the implementation of the proposed workflow to cover a wide range of exposure, hazard and risk scenarios’ as part of the aforementioned, publicly available deliverable report.

Building on D6.1, the current deliverable (D6.3) describes the implementation of the proposed RA workflow in the form of an integrated web application implemented via the Enalos platform, which interlinks scientifically and technically a number of tools developed by NanoCommons partners:

- the web-based GUIDEnano tool, which allows users to upload detailed exposure scenarios online, apply a sophisticated external exposure model, that also may include the effect of any mitigation measures applied, and provides activity/process specific estimations of the peak and long-term ENM spatial concentration over time,
- a collection of organism and tissue specific biokinetics models, in particular Physiologically-

Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models, available through the Jaqpot platform, that can provide precise estimates of the true local levels of internal exposure of the organisms to ENMs,

- a kit of tools and strategies for deriving Points-of-Departure (PODs) from dose-response data, which have been expanded to include transcriptomics data in order to provide more accurate, adverse outcome related, biological hazard values at the target tissues and organs that may manifest short-term or long-term exposure related pathophysiological effects.

This list of integrated tools and approaches is being constantly expanded by incorporating state-of-the-art computational tools and methodologies developed by the nanotechnology community into the NanoCommons e-infrastructure. Our aim is to offer a complete and precise RA solution to researchers, industry, and regulatory stakeholders, optimal for the desired level of detail and the availability of relevant reference information (in-house from the user, or accessed via the NanoCommons Knowledge Base, see also Deliverable Report D4.4 on the first implementation of the NanoCommons Knowledge Base) and harmonized with the standard REACH and ECHA guidance frameworks.

For Deliverable 6.3, entitled “Initial version of integrated web-based decision support system for regulators”, we present the components of the workflow in terms of the methodologies, as well as the development of additional tools and the technical and methodological aspects of their linking into a seamless, user-friendly, end-to-end solution that will later provide a good basis for the implementation of Demonstration Case Studies that fulfill the WP9 Tasks. A case study addressing the risk of producing TiO₂ ENMs in a manufacturing environment is presented in detail herein. The case study consists of multiple exposure scenarios and demonstrates the separate use of each software component and the final user-friendly integrated web application, which links the tools together and offers the RA workflow to the community through a graphical user interface (GUI) and informative visualization tools.

This work also aims to provide a detailed, realistic, step-by-step paradigm of the workflow in action in order to facilitate the adoption of reliable, evidence-based and validated decision-making tools and and to inspire the wider adoption of such web-based tools by the ENM industry and regulators.

2. Summary of risk assessment workflow

In Deliverable D6.1 we described the novel NanoCommons RA workflow that the user can follow to define an exposure scenario and perform exposure, hazard and finally RA (Figure 1). The first step for creating an exposure scenario(s) is to gather the data regarding the ENM of interest. In particular, its physicochemical properties, and detailed information related to the process (during which exposure may occur), the duration of the exposure, the exposed organism(s) as well as ecological data -if available- are incorporated into each scenario. The checklist provided in Deliverable 6.1 is valuable in organizing the data collection process. When both the exposure level and the relevant hazard reference point are available, the calculation of the RCR is direct. If this is not the case, the NanoCommons RA workflow suggests many alternative modelling tools and approaches for estimating the exposure levels and predicting the hazard reference points (RPs).

Figure 1: Flowchart of the NanoCommons nanoinformatics-based RA workflow.

The web-based guidance tool, developed initially through the EU FP7 project GUIDEnano and further optimised and expanded in several additional projects, allows for a complete RA for ENMs and similar products from their production to their waste management. It includes an extensive list of more than 200 processes that are involved throughout the ENM life cycle to choose from and to further specify the exposure conditions, such as the volume and the compartments of space in which the release of

the ENM happens and the relevance to the ENM source, the presence of exposure modifying measures. Then the GUIDEnano tool performs elaborate external exposure simulations that provide accurate Predicted Environmental Concentrations (PEC) or personal exposure concentration estimates depending on the route of exposure, for example inhalation, dermal, or oral.

In the proposed NanoCommons RA workflow, we introduced the concept of extending and tailoring the RA process to the specific characteristics of individuals, through the integration of PBPK models, which predict the internal exposure levels, i.e. the mass/concentration of the ENMs that reaches the systemic circulation, the organs, and tissues of an individual, following the injection, ingestion, or inhalation of the ENM. Consequently, for a more precise risk estimation, the actual internal exposure levels of tissues that might be severely affected by the exposure can be obtained using the appropriate PBPK model for the specific organism (and ENM). This type of modeling can be performed on an individual basis, by incorporating toxicokinetic information about the substance, such as the adsorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) processes, as well as somatometric, and physiological parameters of the exposed individual (sex, age, Body Mass Index), in order to derive the ENM concentrations in various body compartments.

For estimating the hazard Reference Points (RPs), the NanoCommons RA workflow includes three hazard quantification approaches:

- The Benchmark Dose (BMD) modeling approach, that can be applied to available dose-response data;
- The Read-across and/or nano Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship (QSAR) approach assuming the availability of relevant fully validated predictive models;
- The GUIDEnano similarity module and reference database, which provides a list of Final Safety Limit Values (FSLVs), which depend on the exposure setting and the RA hypothesis.

When internal exposure levels can be obtained using the PBPK model, tissue specific RPs should be acquired to provide local threshold limits that define safe use and exposure levels for the specific ENM. For this purpose, methodologies that stem from the dose-dependent nature of the molecular level perturbations, caused by the ENM exposure, such as coupling BMD modelling with toxicogenomics data analysis via the Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) concept, are used to calculate Mechanism-of-Action (MOA)-related points of departure (PODs). This is described in greater detail in the case study implementation.

3. GUIDEnano

3.1. General information

As described extensively in D.6.1 (Sarimveis *et al.*, 2019), GUIDEnano is an interactive web-based Guidance Tool that aims to guide ENM producers and ENM-enabled product manufacturers towards the safe and sustainable design of their ENM-enabled products (Fernandez-Cruz *et al.*, 2018). This tool first was developed during the GUIDEnano European project (FP7-NMP-2013-LARGE-7) and later tested and validated during caLIBRAte project (H2020-NMP-2015-two-stage). A complete tutorial on the use of the GUIDEnano RA tool, developed within NanoCommons, is available (<https://www.guidenano.eu/>). GUIDEnano combines a range of predictive models, multi-level decision trees, and databases to derive critical information along the RA and assess the impact of risk mitigation processes. In the context of this deliverable, GUIDEnano is used to assess the release of ENMs and estimate the occupational exposure profiles, which is the first step in the proposed NanoCommons RA workflow. The ENM, activity, compartment and exposure modules of GUIDEnano are used only. The hazard and the risk assessment and management module are not used. In the following section the ENMs, activity, compartment and exposure modules are detailed.

Figure 3: General overview of the GUIDEnano conceptual framework developed during the GUIDEnano project (<https://www.guidenano.eu/>).

3.2. GUIDEnano parametrization of the Nanomaterials module

The (nano)material module is the section where the user defines all the exposure scenario relevant materials, substances, nano-objects and nano-enabled products and articles. Information about each

ENM should be provided including the under-lying components, chemicals, and their roles. To create a material entry, the user selects the type (article, substance/mixture, nano-object, nanostructured aggregate or nanostructured agglomerate), and adds a name, a short description, the respective category (article, nanoparticles, composite etc), as well as nano-constituent, chemical and hazard information. Within GUIDEnano, an ENM is currently considered to be either a Nano-object or a Nanostructured-object as defined by the ISO/TS 80004-1:2010.

The description of the materials contains information on the physico-chemical properties, the different constituents (core, shell, impurity) and information on the presence of the material in the processes that are included in the activity and the compartment GUIDEnano module, to which the tools provides a direct link (see below).

Firstly, in the physico-chemical properties there are 10 entries, as follows:

- Material(s) identification i.e., source, supplier, origin and a description.
- The shape and size i.e., morphology, mean size and primary size distribution.
- Physical properties i.e., physical state, rigidity, dustiness, melting and boiling point.
- Surface properties i.e., surface specific charge, hydrophilicity/hydrophobicity, and solubility.
- Function i.e., multiple-choice such as binder, photocatalyst, reinforcing agent.
- Mass conversion: in order to specify if the results are displayed in mass, moles, volume, or particle numbers.
- Chemical information to inform the degree of purity (more information can be added when entering information on the different constituents).
- Reactivity information: multiple-choice such as solubility, sulfidation, oxidation.
- Classification and labeling choice from the Global Harmonized System (GHS).
- Toxicity studies where all toxicity added by the user are referenced.

Secondly, the constituent information is provided for each constituent; a tab appears with specific property groups to address. The relevant property groups depend on the category (material-class) used as input together with its role (i.e. core, wall, shell, coating, and impurities). For example, for a solid constituent, applied as a coating, the properties to fill will be the following:

- CAS number / EC number.
- Molecular formula or a molecular group.
- Physical properties of a chemical.
- In the case of a solid, the user enters information on rigidity and crystalline structure.
- Reactivity info: The user can enter the solubility (high, moderate, low, and insoluble) and can select different reactivity.

- Classification & Labelling: The user can indicate if the constituent is labeled with any hazard statements according to the GHS.

Thirdly, the nanomaterials presence: This section is autofilled by the model according to the information provided in the compartment and activity modules.

3.3. GUIDEnano parametrization of the Compartment module

This module is used to describe which “system” or “environmental compartments” the released materials enter first before getting in contact with the exposed species. There are two groups of compartment types: the system compartment, which includes the sewage system, the wastewater treatment plant, the indoor air (room) and the landfill site, and the environmental compartment, which corresponds to fresh water, estuarine, marine, freshwater sediment, saltwater sediment, outdoor air and soil. All compartments are organized in the same way, and further subdivided into General information and Zones. In the General information subsection, the user enters the properties of each relevant Compartment providing information on their sizes and a brief description.

For each compartment considered, the user defines the zones and provides the following zone-specific information:

- **Properties:** temperature and pressure.
- **Composition:** this information is pre-filled by the GUIDEnano tool with standardized values for well known zones (air, sea water, fresh water).
- **Chemical speciation:** define the speciation of each chemical (if known).
- **Contact zone:** the user defines the type of contact between zones (virtually or physically) and their orientation (within, below, etc.).
- **Emission(s):** this entry is connected to the Activity module, and specifies the zone where the ENMs are released (i.e., Near Field (NF)).
- **Processes:** auto-filled by GUIDEnano and summarizes the processes involved in driving the ENMs behavior in the specific zone (i.e. emission from activity, gravitational settling, natural flow air etc.).
- **Kinetics:** auto-filled by GUIDEnano, it provides the results of the simulations run by the GUIDENano Exposure Module on the kinetics of particle concentration over time. The data is provided for each size category of different materials released separately. Informative Mass Concentration versus Time graphs are also generated automatically. This information is the output of GUIDEnano as described below.
- **Exposure agent:** the user chooses the materials of interest for the RA (link to the exposure module).
- **Exposed:** the user defines the exposed population (link to the exposure module).

For a better understanding of this approach, the Near Field /Far Field (NF/FF) model description (available in D 6.1) is presented below.

Two-Box Nano-specific model

The model is based on the NF - FF source receptor model developed by Cherrie, 2009 and Cherrie et al, 2011 and the algorithms developed by Maynard and Zimmer, 2003 for estimating the time evolution of the Particle Size Distribution (PSD) of ENMs. In a two-box (or source-receptor) model the room is typically split into two boxes, one is placed either around the worker or NF source, while the other is the remainder of the room (FF). We located a box around the source and call this the Local Control Influencing zone (LCIZ) to differentiate from the workers-NF zone and the remainder of the room (FF), which is referred to as in the original model by Cherrie *et al* (2011).

Since the worker moves around the room, the concentration in the worker NF zone can be estimated from the concentrations in the LCIZ and FF zones and the time the worker spends in each zone. The concentration in either zone is then a function of agglomeration, diffusion, dispersion, dilution and emission (of the ENMs), with each size bin in each zone (LCIZ or FF) being described using the following equations:

$$\frac{dn(b_j)_{LCIZ}}{dt} = LC * S_{LCIZ} - n(b_j)_{LCIZ} \frac{Q_{LCIZ}}{V_{LCIZ}} + n(b_j)_{FF} \frac{Q_{LCIZ}}{V_{LCIZ}} + \eta_{LCIZ}$$

$$\frac{dn(b_j)_{FF}}{dt} = S_{FF} + n(b_j)_{NF} \frac{Q_{LCIZ}}{V_{FF}} - n(b_j)_{FF} \frac{Q_{LCIZ}}{V_{FF}} - n(b_j)_{FF} \frac{Q_{FF}}{V_{FF}} + \eta_{FF}$$

where

LCIZ is a virtual zone that represents the area of influence of any exposure control around the source,

Q_{LCIZ} is the volume air flow between the LCIZ and FF (m^3/sec),

Q_{FF} represents the ventilation (m^3/sec), and represents the mass emission rate into the LCIZ and FF, respectively in particles/sec,

LC represents the local control adjustment factor, and

η represents the size-specific factors (coagulation, diffusion and dispersion).

3.4. GUIDEnano parametrization of the Activity module

The Activity module allows the user to define all relevant activities (organized in the right order and connected to each other by the materials flow) within all stages of the life cycle of the nano-enabled product/article. To describe an activity, the user fills in the information to the following tabs:

General Info:

- Description
- Setting/scale
- Handing type
- Life cycle phase
- Location (link to the compartment module)
- Applied energy level (drop-down menu with 6 levels)

In the tab Input, output and release

- The user defines the kind and the amount of each ENM used within the activity using one input connector and multiple output and release connector(s), describing the activity through the mass balance of the involved ENMs. Reference rate (i.e., for a pouring activity) does not have to be filled. Release connectors are used to define the intended or incidental release amount/fractions of nano (enabled) materials towards the environmental compartments. A release connector is also used to enable direct contact exposure scenarios.

Duration tab

- The Duration tab is used to define the time “properties” of an activity. In the entry “Activity repetition”, the user has to indicate if an activity is repeated and if so, how many times (for the same batch!). If an activity is repeated, two ways can be used to describe this:
 - 1. the user can enter a fixed number of times within a given timespan,
 - 2. the user can enter the frequency within a given timespan.
- The total time needed to complete an activity once is defined as an **activity cycle**. The time between two cycles is defined as **idle time**. The **operational time**, or period, is the time needed to complete the activity based on the given (input or output) rate and (input or output) amount of material involved.

Nanomaterials flow tab:

This tab receives the input from the compartment and activity sections.

Local controls tab:

- In this tab, the user can enter information from local control using an autofill mode or a library of standard control measures included in GUIDEnano.

3.5. GUIDEnano parametrization of the Exposure module

The Exposure module enables the user to define multiple exposure scenarios for both human populations and environmental populations throughout the entire product life cycle. For human populations, the user can fill in General info, such as the population name, description, and category (workers, consumers, bystanders, etc.). Also, bodyweight and information about working frequency can be provided, otherwise, default values are used.

Available Protective Controls: In the case of a worker population, the user can indicate which personnel protective equipment (PPE) is implemented.

Human exposure paths: The tool supports both occupational and consumer exposure scenarios for three exposure routes: inhalation, dermal and oral. An exposure scenario is defined as a combination of one or more exposure paths related to the same exposure relevant (nano)material.

Indirect exposure (path): When a population gets in contact with the exposure relevant material due to its presence in the zone medium, the contact path is considered indirect. The user defines each indirect exposure path by selecting Exposure zone (Factory NF, Factory FF) and exposure Route (inhalation, dermal and oral), the tool indicates the corresponding Exposure relevant material.

For each defined exposure path, the Concentration estimate(s) and the Protective Equipment can be selected (from a library) or defined by the user. For the Concentration estimate(s) the user can select different methods and models to estimate the materials' release concentration for a defined exposure path. In addition, the user can also enter an estimated value or measured data.

In the case study demonstrating the NanoCommons RA workflow, occupational exposure to TiO₂ ENM by inhalation of released TiO₂ in the NF and FF zone was derived from the Zone derived (fate model) estimate.

4. PBPK modelling

PBPK modelling offers a methodology for predicting the internal distribution and exposure of an ENM in an organism, which can be of particular importance in an RA workflow. PBPK models are mechanistic; they consist of compartments representing real organs and tissues, whose number varies based on the target substance, species, administration route and available information. The compartments of a PBPK model are usually interconnected through the arterial and venous blood pools; all organs receive blood from the arterial blood compartment and the outflow ends up in the venous blood compartment. The blood loop is closed by the lungs compartment, in which the blood flow is reversed in comparison to the rest of the organs. Apart from the regional blood flows, the underlying physiology also defines the second set of substance-independent parameters, the organ volumes. Besides these physiological parameters, PBPK models incorporate information about the target substance as well, through the substance-dependent parameters, which can be obtained using data generated by *in vivo*, *in vitro* or *in silico* experiments.

PBPK models have inherent advantages due to their mechanistic nature compared to empirical biokinetics models. Firstly, they enable predictions of concentration/mass profiles of individual organs and not just of plasma. In addition, their relation with physiology and modularity facilitate the integration of literature information, making predictions prior to *in vivo* experiments possible (Nestorov, 2001). Lastly, their biggest advantage is the ability to perform inter-species (e.g. from rat to human) or intra-species (e.g. from adults to children) extrapolation through scaling methods.

4.1. R function for deploying PBPK models on Jaqpot

NTUA has developed all the necessary infrastructure to develop, host and share PBPK models through the Jaqpot computational platform. The last development comprises the creation of a generic R function, `deploy.pbpk()`, that enables the deployment of virtually any PBPK model on Jaqpot. The format of the function is such that it allows the upload of almost any model, no matter how peculiar or complex its structure is.

The main R library that renders the simulation of PBPK mass/concentration-time profiles on Jaqpot possible, by solving the user-provided ordinary differential equations (ODEs), is DeSolve (Soetaert et al., 2010). Therefore, the building-blocks of `deploy.pbpk()` have been designed and are combined in a way that is in line with functions included in the DeSolve package. The function call is described in the following section:

```
deploy.pbpk(user.input, predicted.feats, create.params, create.inits, create.events, custom.func,
ode.func, method = "lsodes", ...)
```

- i. `user.input`: a list containing the names of the input features inserted by the end-user on the Jaqpot user interface (UI).
- ii. `predicted.feats`: a vector of predicted feature names that will be the final output on the UI. All predicted features included in the list must be part of the output of the differential equations function (`ode.func`). If not, an error is flagged. However, the user can select a subset of the output and present this on the Jaqpot UI instead of the whole output. This should be preferred in the case of vast models

in terms of output dimensions, so that the final result is more readable by the end-user.

iii. `create.params`: a function that receives as input the input of the user (`user.input`) and transforms it according to the needs of the model.

iv. `create.inits`: a function that receives as input the output of `create.params` and creates the initial conditions of the ODEs.

v. `create.events`: a function that receives as input the output of `create.params` and creates a dataframe containing events that force changes on the state variables of the ODE system.

vi. `custom.func`: a custom function that is forwarded to `ode.func` to satisfy the needs of the model.

vii. `ode.func`: a function that is forwarded to `ode()` function of R package `deSolve` and contains the ODEs. The function is requested in the following format:

```
ode.func(integration.time, Initial.Values, Parameters, custom.func)
```

viii. `method`: the user can select a specific solver from the ones provided in the `deSolve` package.

ix. ... → additional arguments passed down to the solver, e.g. relative (`'rtol'`) and absolute (`'atol'`) tolerances.

These lists and functions are utilised by `Jaqpote` behind the scenes and are combined with the end-user's input to produce the desired time profiles on the `Jaqpote` UI.

In Annex A1, an example illustrates how the different blocks of `deploy.pbpk()` should be formatted, by simulating a very simple PBPK model for intravenous injection in rats and contained to two blood pools (`Art_blood`, `Ven_blood`), liver (`Li`), lungs (`Lu`) and a compartment for the rest of the body (`Rob`). The `Jaqpote` UI will allow the end-user to insert a weight for the rat, the doses received intravenously as well as the times at which those doses were administered. The result of the simulation will present only the liver concentration, which the modeler considered as being the most important element of the model (instead of the concentrations of all 5 compartments).

Upon execution of the function, the user selects where the model is uploaded, in most cases the response should be <https://api.jaqpote.org/>, and then an authentication method for logging into the `Jaqpote` system. The latter includes two options: a login with `Jaqpote` user credentials, which requires typing a username and then a password into a prompt message box, or through an application programming interface (API) key, which is acquired from the `Jaqpote` UI. Following that, the user is requested to provide a model title, which remains unaltered, and a short model description, which can be further processed through the `Jaqpote` UI, as described in D.6.1. Finally, the user is informed about the success of the upload process and gets a unique model ID. Figure 4 presents the deployment process.

```
> deploy.pbpk(user_input, predicted.feats, create.params, create.inits, create.events,
+             custom.func, ode.func, method = "lsodes")
Base path of jaqpote *e.g.: https://api.jaqpote.org/ : https://api.jaqpote.org/
Please choose authentication method ([1]=login / [2]=Provide Api Key): 1
Username: PeriklisTs
Title of the model: This is a test PBPK model
Short description of the model: This is a short test version of a larger PBPK model for a chemical compound
[1] "Model created. The id is: ZVccNx2D0ltL9VjL4ljL . Please visit the application to further document your model."
```

Figure 4: Model deployment on `Jaqpote`.

In the near future this function will become part of a greater library that will contain several R wrappers for Jaqpot. At the moment, a user can upload a PBPK model (or a model described by ODEs in general) on Japot by running the `utils.R` and `deploy_pbpk.R` functions available at <https://github.com/KinkyDesign/jaqpotr/tree/test/R>.

5. AOP-based transcriptional BMD modeling and ENM grouping

To address Task 6.2, concerning the development of robust and reliable ENM grouping and read-across methods and tools, NTUA developed a complete workflow that couples the classic toxicogenomics analysis with dose-response modeling. This aims at incorporating detailed biological information about adverse outcome pathways (AOPs) into grouping of ENMs according to their molecular effects, that have been causally associated with specific pathophysiological changes. The proposed workflow takes advantage of the data generated from high-throughput exposure experiments of model organisms to extract the molecular profiles that are attributed to the exposure to a specific ENM.

The usefulness of the implementation of whole gene expression profiling methods on samples from model organisms, such as *M. musculus*, followed by robust bioinformatics analysis pipelines of elaborate computational tools to study the toxicity of specific ENMs has been proven by several studies (for the exposure to carbon black ENMs and various MWCNTs molecular profiles, see Bourdon *et al.*, 2012, Poulsen *et al.*, 2013, Poulsen *et al.*, 2015). Of special interest and focus has been the pulmonary response to exposure to ENM and the molecular mechanisms that cause tissue damage (for exposure to nano-TiO₂, see Husein *et al.*, 2013, Halapannavar *et al.*, 2015). A remarkably interesting result of the aforementioned studies is that regardless of the class of the ENM under investigation, the exposure to ENMs caused the same molecular perturbations at the gene expression and pathway levels, which successively lead to the same, common pathophysiological phenotype, despite the revealed significant differences in the severity of the effect reflected in the number of genes and their respective intensity (fold-change).

In the effort to clarify, encode, organize and understand the molecular events that lead to the manifestation of specific Adverse Outcomes (AO) following the exposure to a substance, the concept of AOPs was initially developed in the context of ecotoxicological risk assessment. The representation of the existing biological knowledge in the form of AOPs captures the causal sequence of events starting with a directly associated response to the exposure, a so-called Molecular Initiating Event (MIE), and ending with the AO via a series of intermediate Key Events (KE) that occur at different levels of biological organization (Ankley *et al.* 2010).

Since the concept of AOPs has become increasingly popular, due to their favorable properties (see more details on AOPs and the integration of a nano-specific MIE prediction tool in NanoCommons Deliverable D5.7), omics approaches have been employed to associate the exposure to ENMs with the activation of specific, already known, well described AOPs or to develop new ones, and to provide useful insights for hazard estimation. The results of these analyses can be further used as input to read-across and grouping methods and in human risk assessment, in relation to apical endpoints and having taken account of the introduced cross-species uncertainty by e.g. adjusting uncertainty factors

(Kuempel *et al.*, 2015). In the case of RA, quantitative information on the MIEs and/or KEs is required to establish a threshold for the occurrence of an apical AO. Since a few studies have already reported that the global changes in gene expression that arise from specific ENM exposures are linked to the manifestation of specific molecular phenotypes in a dose-dependent manner (Halappanavar *et al.*, 2015), dose-response modeling is relevant for the estimation of such molecular Reference Points (RP).

Indeed, dose-response modeling is a modern approach to derive the POD, or RP, to calculate the safe or acceptable margins of exposure (MOE), e.g. for genotoxic and carcinogenic substances. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) and the Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives (JECFA) favor the use of the BMD method to overcome the limitations of the No Observed Adverse Effect Level (NOAEL) / Lowest Observed Adverse Effect Level (LOAEL) (a detailed comparison between the BMD and the NOAEL/LOAEL approaches is provided in Deliverable D6.1, section 4). The derived BMD value is defined as the dose (or concentration) of a substance that corresponds to a low but measurable change in response, namely the benchmark response (BMR), which is predetermined and usually set to 5 or 10% change in the response rate, relative to the response of the control group.

The dose dependent nature of the molecular changes due to the ENM exposure provides a basis for extension of BMD modeling to incorporate the respective quantitative gene expression data (Thomas *et al.*, 2007, 2011, 2013). Thus, the robustness of the BMD method to accurately identify the doses that lead to a significant change in the gene or pathway response in comparison to control samples and in relation to standard BMDs for humans, and the consequent usefulness of the derived transcriptional/pathway BMDs to serve as PODs for ENM-induced toxicity for RA, have been reported by Halappanavar *et al.* (2019).

Thus, in the Deliverable D6.2 report, we described a case study using publicly available whole genome gene expression data for multiple doses of ENMs, retrieved from the NCBI GEO repository, and state-of-the-art bioinformatics analysis to reveal the patterns of the changes in gene expression that are caused by exposure to a set of TiO₂ ENM. The proposed workflow (Figure 5) consists of three parts, starting with the comprehensive toxicogenomics analysis to identify the genes that have been over- or underexpressed due to exposure to each ENM. This results in differentially expressed gene lists that are further projected onto ontological trees of terms that crystallize the established knowledge on biological processes at gene level as well as the signaling and metabolic pathways (Figure 5, I). The second part applies the BMD method for each one of the differentially expressed genes identified in the first step and computes the respective transcriptional BMD (BMDt) value per affected gene or summarizes the BMDt at the affected pathway level (Figure 5, II). The last part combines the results of the second part with data retrieved from public databases to provide a hierarchical grouping of the ENMs by their ability to affect the pathways associated with a specific AO of an AOP of interest (Figure 5, III). Figure 6 is a schematic representation of the results of the various steps of the workflow.

Figure 5: Overview of the NanoCommons ENM AOP-based grouping workflow as described in Deliverable report D6.2.

Figure 6: Schematic of the NanoCommons ENM AOP-based grouping workflow intermediate and final outputs as described in Deliverable report D6.2.

6. Case study description

The ENM described in this demonstration case study was selected according to multiple criteria. First, the availability of relevant information (i.e. physico-chemical characterization, hazard data) was assessed. We were particularly interested in ENMs that are commercially available, and already in use in the industrial sector that could be good choices for our case study (i.e. the implementation of the complete NanoCommons RA workflow on a set of realistic exposure scenarios describing the occupational exposure through airborne ENMs emitted during powder handling activities). Among the potential ENMs that could be good candidates according to the above criteria, we selected a TiO₂ ENM referred to as NM 102 produced by Cristal Global. The company's description of NM 102 mentions that it is a "Photocatalytic Powder", which "can be suitably formulated and incorporated into exterior coatings, building and construction materials and transportation infrastructure products for roads, paving, and noise barriers. Cristal has experience in the formulation and testing of these materials containing photocatalytic powders as the active ingredient. Photocatalytic functionality as described above can also be beneficial in many other applications such as textiles, roof tiles, etc".

In addition to this, TiO₂ ENM being a commercial product and relevant to an industrial handling setting, it is also included in the repository for Representative Test Materials (RTMs) (Totaro *et al.*, 2016), based on preparatory work started in 2008. The repository supports both EU and international research projects, including the OECD Working Party on Manufactured Nanomaterials (WPMN). An RTM ENM is defined as "a material from a single batch, which is sufficiently homogeneous and stable with respect to one or more specified properties, and which implicitly is assumed to be fit for its intended use in the development of test methods which target properties other than the properties for which homogeneity and stability have been demonstrated". All these NMs are well characterized, with the methods used and the detailed results extensively described in Rasmussen *et al.* (2015). In our case study, a set of relevant data was retrieved from the NM-102 Dossier and used in the GUIDEnano tool as input for the ENM physico-chemical properties section.

Figure 7: TEM image of NM-102 extracted from Rasmussen *et al.* (2015).

The availability of toxicokinetic and toxicogenomic data for the ENM of choice is also an important prerequisite for the implementation of our multi-step RA workflow but these types of data are usually scarce, segmented or even incomplete. In many cases, the complete characterization of the ENM used in the experiments is missing, or there is no available data for the same organism, which renders

making any comparisons and drawing robust conclusions from them more difficult and uncertain.

The species on which the full RA workflow was applied was mice. This selection was made, because for the BMD modelling and analysis part of the workflow, full gene expression data after exposure to TiO₂ are only available for this species. For PBPK modelling, concentration-time data were available for rats, therefore a PBPK model was developed first for rats and then it was extrapolated to mice. Several external exposure scenarios were constructed and simulated in GUIDEnano. The outputs of these scenarios were provided as inputs to the PBPK model for estimating the amount of TiO₂ in several tissues of the body as a function of time. Finally the risk of triggering AOP 173, entitled “Secretion of inflammatory cytokines leading to lung fibrosis”, and/or particular pathways involved in AOP 173 was computed by comparing the estimated internal ENM weight in the lungs of the mice with the safe weight levels derived by applying the BMD analysis on relevant gene expression data.

The next section illustrates that the various tools and services developed by different partners in the NanoCommons project can be scientifically and technically interlinked to implement this integrated RA and decision support workflow, which will also be submitted for publication to a scientific journal.

7. Case study implementation

7.1. External Exposure Modeling using GUIDEnano

7.1.1. Detailed description of the ENM in the exposure scenario.

As described previously, TiO₂ NMs are used as photocatalytic agents in diverse products. For example, they are added to cement and paints wherein they show photocatalytic properties. Furthermore, this NM shows self-cleaning and air depollution properties providing additional environmental benefits as well as reducing the maintenance cost. On the other hand, there are also a few potential risks associated with the TiO₂ NM life cycle, with the most important being worker exposure to TiO₂ aerosol when handling TiO₂ NM powder before its incorporation into the different product matrix formulations (i.e. paint, plastic, cement). Thus, we opted to focus our exposure scenario on the process of pouring TiO₂ NM powder in a paint factory hall prior to blending it in the paint matrix.

7.1.2. Data entry in the GUIDEnano Nanomaterials module for our case study

Table 1: Resume of the data entry for the GUIDEnano nanomaterials module.

Nanomaterials module		
Data extracted Rasmussen <i>et al.</i> (2015). Titanium Dioxide, NM-100, NM-101, NM-102, NM-103, NM-104, NM-105: Characterisation, and Physico-Chemical Properties. JRC Science and Policy Reports. Publications Office of the European Union, JRC Repository: NM-series of representative manufactured nanomaterials, Joint Research Centre, Ispra, Italy. (Table 61)		
Identification	Name	TiO ₂ NM102
	Description	CristalACTiV™ Ultrafine titanium dioxide (TiO ₂) photocatalysts, leads the development of photocatalytic formulations and has developed testing and monitoring techniques in a number of formulated downstream applications such as coatings and paints.
	Origin	Engineered
	Source/supplier	Cristal Global bought by Tronox (USA), CAS 13463-67-7
Shape and Size	Shape	Spherical
	Size distribution available	yes
	Method used	TEM
	Size type	Primary size
	Metric of size distribution	mass

	Mean size	22 nm
	Standard deviation	2.2 nm (10% of the mean size). To simplify the case study, the SD was chosen to obtain nanoparticles in only one predetermined size category.
Physical properties	Physical state	Solid
	Size category this solid materials present	nanoscale particles (1 nm –30 nm) Considering the mean size and the SD, 100% of particles are in between 1 and 30 nm.
	Rigidity	Rigid
	Dustiness [mg/kg]:	15
Surface properties	Layout and charge	Chemical compound: TiO ₂ NM102, Role: core
Other properties	function	photocatalyst
	Chemical info	Are all constituents, impurities and contaminants added and identified? Yes. Purity in % :100
Constituents	Mass density	4 g/cm ³
	Select constituents	Category: chemical, name/identifier: TiO ₂ NM102 (CAS No.13463-67-7), phase: solid, role of constituent: core,conc.:100 ,unit: %,mass perc.: 100%

7.1.3. Case Study Compartment information

For our exposure scenario we intend to assess the risk associated with the handling of TiO₂ NM powder in a large scale industrial place, such as a factory hall, thus two separate compartments are to be considered: the indoor, which includes the Near Field, the Far Field and the Floor zones, and the outdoor one. The outdoor compartment is restricted solely to the outdoor air excluding the soil. We opted to focus our risk analysis on the exposure of TiO₂ NMs through inhalation in the factory mixing hall. For the modeling it was assumed that the activity was taking place in a paint factory similar to the one described in Koivisto *et al.* (2015) (20 m wide, 30 m long and 2.5 m height). As described in this paper, the air exchange in the paint formulation room (i.e., where TiO₂ NM powder is poured into the paint matrix and the paint and TiO₂ NM powder are mixed) was maintained by natural ventilation where most of the air was assumed to exchange through two pairs of doors that were open all the time onto a loading ramp. In a mixing station, raw materials in powder form were poured through a quadratic opening (0.8 × 0.8 m²) into a mixing tank located below the mixing room. The near field size was set to 2 × 2 × 2 m².

7.1.4. Data entry in GUIDEnano Compartment module for our case study

Table 2: Resume of the data entry for the GUIDEnano compartment module.

Compartment module		
	Select compartment	Type: indoor air, Name: Factory hall
		Type outdoor air, Name: factory hall
General	Name	Factory hall
	With of the room	20 m
	Length of the room	30 m
	Volume of the room	1500 m ³
Zones	Select zone	Zone description: NF (Local Control Influencing Zone, LCIZ), Number: 1, Medium: air, Size: 8, Unit: m ³ , Total dimension: 8 m ³ .
	Select zone	Zone description: Floor, Number: 1, Medium: solid, Size: 600, Unit: m ² , Total dimension: 600 m ² .
	Select zone	Zone description: Rest of the room (FF), Number: 1, Medium: air, Size: 1492, Unit: m ³ , Total dimension: 1492 m ³
Zones: near field	Properties	Temperature: 25.0 °C.
	Contact zones	In contact with: Floor, Orientation: below, Separated: virtually. In contact with: Rest of the Room (FF), Orientation: around, Separated: virtually.
	Exposed	Select or add a new exposed human population or ecological species: Workers exposure NF (LCIZ).
Zone: Floor	Properties	Temperature: 25.0 °C.
	Contact zones	In contact with: NF (LCIZ), Orientation: above, Separated: virtually. In contact with: Rest of the Room (FF), Orientation: above, Separated: virtually.
	Exposed	Select or add a new exposed human population or ecological species: Workers exposure Floor.
Zone: Rest of the	Properties	Temperature: 25.0 °C, Pressure: 1 atm., Mechanical ventilation: Yes, Air exchanges per hour [/h]: 4

Room (FF)	Contact zones	In contact with: NF (LCIZ), Orientation: within, Separated: virtually. In contact with: Floor, Orientation: below, Separated: virtually. In contact with: Outdoor air (outside of the factory hall) outdoor air, Orientation: around, Separated: physically.
	Exposed	Select or add a new exposed human population or eco species: Workers exposure Rest of the room (FF).

7.1.5. Case Study Activity information

For the purpose of this deliverable, a set of 4 exposure scenarios were generated. The rationale is that they correspond to small-medium or large amounts of NMs being handled, that describe realistic industrial conditions. Thus, the input differs only in the mass involved in the Activity module. One key parameter in the NF/FF model is the characterization of the source emission rate and how well it describes emissions in the occupational environment. For a particulate matter (PM) generated by powder handling, the source term is usually characterized by a dustiness index. The concept of the dustiness index was developed to classify bulk materials according to their relative dust-producing capacity, however, it is an empirically defined property (Jensen *et al.*, 2016). Despite its use as an endpoint of a functional assay for aerosol concentration (Fonseca *et al.*, 2017), there are limitations that arise from the measurement method. However, it is considered as the best measurement to use as an estimate of the dust production. We assume the release percentage as being constant and unchanged with the total amount of TiO₂ involved.

For the 4 exposure scenarios generated for this Deliverable, 3000, 2000, 500 and 175 kg total amounts of TiO₂ NM powder were assumed to be handled (Cases 1, 2, 3, and 4 respectively). The exposed worker is pouring TiO₂ bags for 1 minute in every hour, meaning 1 min pouring and 59 min idle time. This operation is repeated 7 times within the working day, with the same amount of NM powder handled by each pouring cycle, as depicted in the schematic view in Figure 8.

Figure 8 : Schematic view of the activity timeline over the 8 hours.

Table 3: Resume of the initial mass of TiO₂ NM powder poured and the associated mass released as dust for each case study.

	Initial mass of TiO ₂ poured (kg)	Mass released of TiO ₂ (g)
Case 1	3000	45
Case 2	2000	30
Case 3	500	7.5
Case 4	175	2.6

Table 4: Description of the activity timeline, the quantity (mass of NM powder) poured per hour and the total duration of pouring. The release rate is defined according to the mass released solely during the activity time.

	Total duration	Activity time / hour	Mass poured per hour (kg)	Release rate by location (during activity time)
Case 1	7 hours	1 min	428	107.1 mg/s
Case 2	7 hours	1 min	285	71.4 mg/s
Case 3	7 hours	1 min	71	17.8 mg/s
Case 4	7 hours	1 min	25	6.25 mg/s

As mentioned previously, the ENM release rate for the pouring activity is estimated by the dustiness index as described below:

Release rate in %: Total mass released divided by total mass involved in the activity. Mass emission rate from (Jensen *et al.*, 2016). The emission rate, calculated by the small rotating drum dustiness test method = 15 mg/kg (dustiness index), is converted to % giving 0.0015%.

7.1.6. Data entry in the GUIDEnano Activity module for our case study

In the following table the full data input is presented as it was input into the GUIDEnano tools with CS1, CS2, CS3, and CS4 being the abbreviations for case studies 1, 2, 3, and 4, respectively.

Table 5: Resume of the data entry for the GUIDEnano activity framework.

Activity module		
General info	Name	Pouring X kg TiO ₂ - NM102
	Setting scale	Large industry
	Handling type	Manual

	Applied energy level	Medium
	Life cycle phase	Production
	Concurrent locations	Factory hall, Near field
Input, output and release	Activity input	TiO ₂ NM poured during the activity, Material: TiO ₂ NM102, Total amount: CS1= 175, CS2=500, CS3=2000, CS4=3000, Unit: kg, Ref.: yes, Rate:
	Activity output	TiO ₂ contained in the formulated paint, Material: TiO ₂ anatase, Relative to: Input/ TiO ₂ NM poured during the activity, Relative amount: 99.9%, Total amount: CS1=174.9, CS2= 499.9, CS3= 1999.9 and CS4=2999.9 Unit: kg, Ref.: no.
	Activity release	Emitted particles into the room (indoor), Material: TiO ₂ anatase, Relative to: Input TiO ₂ NM poured during the activity, Relative release: 0.00015%, RMM: no, Total release: CS1=2.6, CS2=7.5, CS3= 30 and CS4= 45, Unit: g, Ref.: no, Rate/location: CS1=6.25, CS2=17.8, CS3= 71.4 and CS4= 107.1 mg/s
Duration	Activity repetition	Number of times this activity is repeated periodically for the same batch 1/h
	Operational repetition	operational time needed to complete one activity cycle: 1 min for an activity operational for 60 min
	Time span	Total time span of all activity cycles together: 7h
(Nano)materials flow	Input	Input: TiO ₂ NMs that are poured during the activity.
	output	Output(s): TiO ₂ NM contained in the formulated paint.
	release	Release(s): Release Particles emitted to room (indoor), Into compartment zone: Factory hall NF (LCIZ)

7.1.7. Exposure information

The GUIDEnano tool can perform a complete RA since it also includes hazard information, either provided by the user or from a database connected to the platform. However, for the purpose of the implementation of the NanoCommons RA assessment workflow, as was previously described, GUIDEnano was restricted to providing output from the simulation results of the External Exposure Concentration, i.e., the concentration of the particles over time in the NF and FF for the 8 hours of the workers' shift. As expected, the higher the total mass of particles, the more dust is emitted. The dust concentrations are predicted using the "zone derived estimate" model.

7.1.8. Data entry in GUIDEnano Activity module for our case study

Table 6: Resume of the data entry for the GUIDEnano exposure module.

Exposure module		
General	Select human populations:	Population name: Workers, Group: workers
	Population name:	Workers
Exposure paths	Select indirect through zones:	Exposure zone(s): factory hall NF (LCIZ), Route(s): inhalation, Exposure relevant material: TiO ₂ NM102.
	Select indirect through zones:	Exposure zone(s): factory hall Rest of the room (FF), Route(s): inhalation, Exposure relevant material: TiO ₂ NM102.
	Select indirect through zones:	Exposure zone(s): factory hall Floor, Route(s): dermal, Exposure relevant material: TiO ₂ NM102.

7.1.9. External Exposure Output of the GUIDEnano tool (as input to a PBPK model)

For the four case studies, the output of the tools is the particle concentration in the NF and FF over time. Each dataset represents a total of 765 and 521 data points in the NF and FF, respectively. Figures 9 and 10 represent a typical dataset for CS1. The concentration-time profiles of all scenarios are presented in Annex 2.

Figure 9: Particle concentration in mass by m³ over time in the NF for case study 1.

Figure 10: Particle concentration in mass by m^3 over time in the Far Field for the case study 1.

7.1.10. Movement between FF and NF

In order to simulate a realistic movement scenario within the factory space defined by the NF and FF, a combination of the two concentration-time profiles was generated. Specifically, the worker was considered to stay for -approximately- the first 90 seconds of each working hour in the NF (throughout all of the TiO_2 pouring activity) and then move for the rest of the hour to the FF, movements which coincide with those of a worker performing this activity. The constructed combined scenario for CS1 is illustrated in Figure 11, while the graphs for all 4 cases are presented in Annex 3. These combined scenarios were the input for the (rat) PBPK model.

Figure 11: Combined concentration - time profile for case study 1.

7.2. PBPK modeling

7.2.1. Development of PBPK model to describe inhalation of TiO₂ ENMs on rat

The development of a PBPK model is a process that includes several steps. A PBPK model is a system of differential equations (DE) that consist of substance-specific and organism-specific parameters. Defining the structure of the DE system requires information about the administration route, organism and substance. Each combination of the three aforementioned elements can lead to a different structure and the goal is to arrive at an optimum formation that best describes the Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion (ADME) of the substance at hand under certain conditions. Naturally, the complexity of the model, i.e., the number of DEs and parameters, is guided by the availability of relevant data. Once the structure of the model is decided, it can be used for several species among the same class (e.g., mammals), by assuming that physiology changes between the species are not significant enough to lead to structural changes in terms of how the biological processing of particles occurs. The decision of the DE system is followed by the parametric declaration. This is a complex procedure, since parametric values can be drawn from several different sources, namely literature data, *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation, *in silico* predictions (e.g., QSARs) or model fitting on *in vivo* biodistribution data. The best strategy is to follow a tiered approach, where the model is refined at each level.

The goal was to create a PBPK model for characterisation of the biodistribution of TiO₂ ENMs in rat after inhalation, with emphasis on the lower respiratory tract. After an extensive search in the literature, no *in vitro* or *in silico* data were found, therefore fitting on *in vivo* data was performed to create the model.

7.2.2. TiO₂ NM inhalation data

Searching for *in vivo* data had, as a first priority, to collect information that refers to inhalation of TiO₂ NMs with a size similar to the one considered by the rest of the tools, namely around 20 nm. Most published studies involved experiments with intratracheal instillation and very few studies included inhalation data. Among these studies, we gave priority to the ones reporting concentration/mass time profiles in a detailed manner for the lower respiratory tract. Specifically, instead of a single record for the lungs, multiple entries were preferred, e.g., trachea, alveolar region etc. Regarding the species, we initially searched for kinetics data for mice, due to the limitation imposed by the availability of gene expression data. However, since no study referring to mice was found in the literature, we searched for data for rats with the aim of developing a PBPK model for rats and mapping it to mice using inter-species extrapolation.

One of the few studies that fulfilled the established criteria was the one of Kreyling *et al.* (2019). It was preferred over other published studies because of the high recovery rate, number of analysed tissues and reporting of mass found in excreta. In their experiment, 20 adult Wistar Kyoto rats were divided into 5 groups and exposed to slightly different doses of ⁴⁸V-radiolabeled 20 nm TiO₂ ENM aerosol for 2 hours via an endotracheal tube. Each group was exsanguinated and dissected for extraction of biodistribution data and the quantities of TiO₂ were calculated indirectly using ⁴⁸V

radioactivity, measured with γ - spectrometry, which was then matched to TiO_2 through mass and radioactivity balances. The first rat group was sacrificed immediately after exposure, and then the second, third, fourth and fifth groups were euthanized 4 hours, 24 hours, 7 days and 28 days post exposure, respectively.

The tissue compartments for which measurements were reported were the total lungs, lavaged lungs, bronchoalveolar lavage cells (BALC), bronchoalveolar lavage fluid (BALF), trachea, liver, spleen, kidneys, heart, brain, uterus, blood, carcass, skeleton, soft tissue, 2nd organs and skin. From those, total lungs, carcass and 2nd organs were not used since they included biodistribution information from combinations of other compartments. The values reported were corrected for residual blood, fast mucociliary clearance and ^{48}V detached from the TiO_2 matrix and were given as a fraction of the initial peripheral lung dose (IPLD), which was equal to the initial lung dose, i.e. the total amount of TiO_2 inhaled and deposited in the system, minus the mass that was cleared through the fast mucociliary clearance mechanism. These fractions were multiplied by the corresponding IPLDs of each group to find the amount of TiO_2 ENMs measured in each tissue for each group. Besides these fractions, mean TiO_2 ENM aerosol mass, total inhaled volume, total deposited fraction, total deposited mass and IPLD per group were extracted from this study.

With regard to excreta, data were not available in a tabular format, but rather given through graphs. For extracting information from the graphs, the freely available plot digitizer Graph Grabber 2.0.2 was utilised. Cumulative feces and urine data were drawn from the respective plots provided in Kreyling *et al.* (2019) for the 28 days exposure rat group.

7.2.3. Structural model

The structural model was mostly guided by the compartments for which biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* were available. The most significant compartments were the trachea, BALF, BALC and lavaged lungs. The nature of the exposure is such that most ENMs get either deposited in the lung region or get excreted, whereas only a small amount is translocated across the air-blood-barrier into the systemic circulation (Kreyling *et al.*, 2019).

Across the literature, the closest model to fit the needs of this study was the one of Li *et al.* (2016), which describes the biodistribution of cerium oxide ENMs in rats after inhalation. The lung biodistribution was expressed through 4 compartments, one for the tracheobronchial region, one for the pulmonary region, one for the interstitium and one for the capillary blood of the lungs. In the first two of the aforementioned compartments the ENMs exist in a “free” state, while in the pulmonary and interstitium regions the ENMs can be endocytosed by phagocytotic cells (PCs). In relation to the rest of the tissues, three sub-compartments were utilised, one for the capillary blood, which comprises the entrance port of the ENM to the tissue, one for the tissue interstitium and a compartment for endocytosed into PCs. The capillary blood exchanges ENMs with the interstitium compartment, which is also in contact with the PCs sub-compartment. This modelling approach was first used in Li *et al.* (2014), in a PBPK for explaining the biodistribution of polyethylene glycol-coated polyacrylamide NMs in rats after intravenous injection.

The structural guidelines set in Li *et al.* (2016) were followed in this work with minor changes. The TiO_2 ENMs enter the system via three compartments, namely the tracheobronchial region, the alveolar

region and the upper airways. Apart from the respiratory tract, the model consists of two blood pools, the arterial and venous, and 9 tissue compartments, namely the liver, spleen, kidneys, heart, brain, gonads, skeleton, skin and soft tissues, which acts as a rest of the body compartment and incorporates all remaining tissues that haven't been stated explicitly. All tissues receive blood from the arterial pool, which acts as the entrance gate of ENMs into the local tissue, and the outgoing blood flow ends in the venous blood pool. The only exception to this scheme is the lung compartment, which acts as a node that closes the blood loop, since it receives blood from the venous blood compartment and the output blood arrives at the arterial blood compartment. Note that for better agreement with physiology, the outflow of the spleen compartment acts as inflow for the liver compartment.

Excretion of the ENMs takes place in three compartments: in the liver, through hepatobiliary excretion from the liver tissue to feces, in the kidneys, where ENMs are excreted to urine, and through a combination of fast mucociliary clearance and long-term macrophage-mediated clearance. Fast mucociliary clearance takes place in the early stages of exposure, while long-term macrophage mediated clearance is a slower continuous process, where endocytosed ENMs move towards the ciliated airways and then end up in the gastrointestinal tract and are subsequently secreted to feces. The model considers a single type of clearance from the lower respiratory tract that combines these two: PCs can move from the alveolar region to the tracheobronchial region, with the latter compartment containing a clearance term for secreting TiO₂ ENMs directly to feces.

The model includes a range of physiological (organism-specific) and substance-specific parameters. In the first group the list contains regional blood flows and tissue volumes, which were drawn from literature (Brown *et al.*, 1997) as percentages of the total cardiac output and total body weight, respectively. The total cardiac output for the rat was calculated from a literature equation that used body weight as a covariate (Brown *et al.*, 1997) and the same calculation rationale was followed for total blood volume (Lee *et al.*, 1985) and inhaled volume rate (EPA, 1994). Another physiological parameter related to the PCs sub-compartment was PC content per organ as a fraction of the organ volume, which was drawn from Aborig *et al.* (2019). Most substance-specific parameters were estimated from the *in vivo* data with the procedure that is analysed in the following section, with the exception of the desorption rate by PCs, mainly due to identification problems.

The schematic presentation of the developed PBPK is illustrated in Figure 12. Annex 4 presents in detail the differential equations and also includes a table which records the units and an explanation of all parameters.

Figure 12: Schematic representation of the TiO₂ PBPK model developed within NanoCommons (this deliverable).

7.2.4. Model fit on *in vivo* data

After defining the structural model, the next step was to integrate the information contained in the data along with prior information found in literature into the parameters of the DE system. This was performed using a dynamic form of Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC), the No-U-Turn Sampler (Hoffman & Gelman, 2014). The sampler stochastically searches the parametric space moving to value combinations that are more likely to have generated the data at hand. The final output is a distribution

for each parameter, thus quantifying the uncertainty of each estimate. Model fitting was performed using the RStan (v.2.17.3) library (Carpenter *et al.*, 2017) in R 3.5.1.

Estimating every substance-specific parameter individually without any grouping would not only be computationally infeasible, but also statistically impossible, due to the identifiability problems that arise from estimating many parameters from the same compartment with limited information. For this reason a lot of different schemes were tested in order to arrive at the most stable parameter grouping that produces the best fit. This was done mainly through trial and error. The final parameterisation involved a single generic permeability coefficient for all tissues, a grouped tissue to blood partition coefficient for the liver and spleen, another grouped partition coefficient for the soft tissues, heart and skeleton and a generic maximum uptake capacity of PCs for all tissues except for the skeleton and alveolar region. All parameters that referred to the clearance of TiO₂ and movement in the upper respiratory tract also had to be estimated. Note that all parameters that were related to the upper respiratory tract were set to zero in order to silence the effect of this compartment, for which there was no information in the experiment of Kreyling *et al.* (2019). The desorption rate by PCs, maximum uptake rate by PCs and hepatobiliary clearance, which were not fitted to the data, were obtained from Li *et al.* (2016). The deposition fractions for the tracheobronchial and alveolar regions were drawn from the Multiple-Path Particle Dosimetry (MPPD) model, v.3.04 (RIVM, 2002), using the same input as that provided in Table S1 in the Supplementary Information of Kreyling *et al.* (2019). After calculating the two deposition fractions, these were normalised using the total deposition fractions reported in Kreyling *et al.* (2019) for each rat group. Finally, clearance from the tracheobronchial region was also not fitted but instead was estimated through MPPD, using the clearance graphs produced by the model. Specifically, since clearance multiplies the mass in the tracheobronchial compartment, clearance rate (h⁻¹) was estimated by taking the clearance rate (mg/day) of the alveolar and tracheobronchial compartments after an hour of exposure (minimum exposure possible) produced by MPPD (first point of the graphs in Figures 13 and 14) and dividing them by the amount of TiO₂ deposited in these two compartments. The resulting clearance was equal to 0.012 h⁻¹.

Figure 13: Alveolar clearance plot produced by MPPD.

Figure 14: Tracheobronchial clearance plot produced by MPPD.

After selecting the parameters to be estimated, the next step was to define their prior distributions. All parameters were considered to be independent of each other and lognormally distributed, with their mean values drawn from Li *et al.* (2016). For all prior distributions, a coefficient of variation (CV) equal to 10% was considered. When higher CVs were tested, convergence problems appeared. With regard to the model likelihood, an additive error model was used, centered around the solution of the ordinary DE system. Three different errors were considered: one for the alveolar, tracheobronchial, lung interstitium and excreta compartments, one for the spleen, heart, brain and uterus compartment, due to the fact that these compartments recorded very low TiO₂ mass accumulation, and one for all the remaining compartments. The statistical model followed is described in more detail in Tsiros *et al.* (2019). Four chains were used in total, for better exploration of the parametric space, each consisting of 1000 iterations, from which 400 iterations were discarded (warm-up period).

The posterior distributions, that are the result of fitting the created model to the data of Kreyling *et al.* (2019), are presented in Figure 16. Convergence was assessed through the Rhat statistic, also known as the potential scale reduction factor, that is reported in the RStan fit output, along with the effective sample size. All parameters had Rhat <1.2, which suggests that convergence has been practically reached (Gelman & Rubin, 1992). In addition to that, the fact that all parameters had an effective sample size equal to the actual number of samples indicates that independency of sample drawings holds. HMC diagnostics provided by RStan were also investigated, for instance divergences, tree depth and E-BFMI, and all tools revealed a good fit (Figure 15). Inspection of individual chains confirmed the conclusions drawn from the diagnostic tools, i.e., that the results have statistical robustness and can be trusted. Figure 17 illustrates an example of a chain and more specifically, it presents the chains containing all post warm-up iterations of the three errors. The plot reveals good mixing and low autocorrelation, an attribute that was witnessed in all parameter chains.

```
Divergences:  
0 of 2400 iterations ended with a divergence.  
  
Tree depth:  
0 of 2400 iterations saturated the maximum tree depth of 10.  
  
Energy:  
E-BFMI indicated no pathological behavior.
```

Figure 15: RStan HMC-specific diagnostic tool results.

4 chains, each with iter=1000; warmup=400; thin=1;
 post-warmup draws per chain=600, total post-warmup draws=2400.

	mean	se_mean	sd	2.5%	25%	50%	75%	97.5%	n_eff	Rhat
sigma[1]	0.09830	0.00027	0.01337	0.07659	0.08861	0.09711	0.10654	0.12762	2400	0.99911
sigma[2]	0.00542	0.00002	0.00088	0.00394	0.00481	0.00532	0.00594	0.00750	2400	1.00013
sigma[3]	0.00012	0.00000	0.00002	0.00009	0.00011	0.00012	0.00013	0.00017	2400	0.99944
theta_tr[1]	-0.36244	0.00204	0.09974	-0.56196	-0.43027	-0.36133	-0.29360	-0.16910	2400	0.99877
theta_tr[2]	-0.34355	0.00199	0.09739	-0.53397	-0.41056	-0.34235	-0.27816	-0.15673	2400	0.99921
theta_tr[3]	-6.93467	0.00188	0.09199	-7.11424	-6.99556	-6.93188	-6.87440	-6.76157	2400	0.99873
theta_tr[4]	-5.76096	0.00180	0.08821	-5.93430	-5.81854	-5.76245	-5.70243	-5.58899	2400	0.99941
theta_tr[5]	-4.60219	0.00204	0.09989	-4.80048	-4.66910	-4.59945	-4.53568	-4.40607	2400	0.99913
theta_tr[6]	-0.07941	0.00193	0.09450	-0.26369	-0.14284	-0.07919	-0.01503	0.10266	2400	0.99893
theta_tr[7]	1.48480	0.00158	0.07753	1.33310	1.43406	1.48338	1.53710	1.64159	2400	1.00088
theta_tr[8]	-3.80082	0.00168	0.08207	-3.96609	-3.85333	-3.80047	-3.74636	-3.63623	2400	0.99970
theta_tr[9]	6.22514	0.00164	0.08019	6.06975	6.17249	6.22574	6.27952	6.37925	2400	1.00002
theta_tr[10]	0.57855	0.00197	0.09666	0.38623	0.51472	0.58113	0.64262	0.76589	2400	1.00005
theta_tr[11]	-5.30532	0.00211	0.10348	-5.50101	-5.37669	-5.30510	-5.23577	-5.10745	2400	0.99858
theta_tr[12]	2.19447	0.00190	0.09290	2.01323	2.13374	2.19496	2.25479	2.37572	2400	0.99914
theta_tr[13]	-1.59524	0.00197	0.09632	-1.77736	-1.66220	-1.59439	-1.52770	-1.40964	2400	0.99970
theta_tr[14]	-2.55549	0.00188	0.09193	-2.73011	-2.61939	-2.55342	-2.49039	-2.37961	2400	0.99877
theta_tr[15]	-1.12578	0.00194	0.09499	-1.30910	-1.18800	-1.12843	-1.06497	-0.93994	2400	0.99914
theta[1]	0.69944	0.00142	0.06974	0.57009	0.65034	0.69675	0.74557	0.84443	2400	0.99876
theta[2]	0.71261	0.00142	0.06933	0.58627	0.66328	0.71010	0.75717	0.85493	2400	0.99922
theta[3]	0.00098	0.00000	0.00009	0.00081	0.00092	0.00098	0.00103	0.00116	2400	0.99886
theta[4]	0.00316	0.00001	0.00028	0.00265	0.00297	0.00314	0.00334	0.00374	2400	0.99929
theta[5]	0.01008	0.00002	0.00101	0.00823	0.00938	0.01006	0.01072	0.01220	2400	0.99921
theta[6]	0.92779	0.00179	0.08778	0.76821	0.86689	0.92386	0.98508	1.10811	2400	0.99899
theta[7]	4.42736	0.00702	0.34414	3.79277	4.19572	4.40781	4.65107	5.16335	2400	1.00084
theta[8]	0.02243	0.00004	0.00184	0.01895	0.02121	0.02236	0.02360	0.02635	2400	0.99981
theta[9]	506.91869	0.82983	40.65310	432.57466	479.37692	505.59709	533.53435	589.48309	2400	0.99990
theta[10]	1.79179	0.00353	0.17307	1.47143	1.67316	1.78805	1.90145	2.15090	2400	1.00023
theta[11]	0.00499	0.00001	0.00052	0.00408	0.00462	0.00497	0.00532	0.00605	2400	0.99858
theta[12]	9.01394	0.01707	0.83611	7.48746	8.44642	8.97961	9.53331	10.75877	2400	0.99914
theta[13]	0.20380	0.00040	0.01965	0.16908	0.18972	0.20303	0.21703	0.24423	2400	0.99966
theta[14]	0.07798	0.00015	0.00716	0.06521	0.07285	0.07782	0.08288	0.09259	2400	0.99872
theta[15]	0.32587	0.00063	0.03107	0.27006	0.30483	0.32354	0.34474	0.39065	2400	0.99923
lp__	342.08684	0.09972	3.03262	335.24919	340.20664	342.47644	344.25353	346.99994	925	1.00118

Samples were drawn using NUTS(diag_e) at Mon Jul 06 19:18:09 2020.
 For each parameter, n_eff is a crude measure of effective sample size,
 and Rhat is the potential scale reduction factor on split chains (at
 convergence, Rhat=1).

Figure 16: Stan fitting results. Theta_tr refers to the parameters in the transformed log space and theta are the parameters in the untransformed space (by taking the exponent of the theta_tr). Sigma[1] refers to the model error of the alveolar tracheobronchial, lung interstitium and excreta compartments, sigma[3] the error of the spleen, heart, brain and uterus compartments and sigma[2] the error of all the other compartments. Theta[1] corresponds to the generic permeability coefficient, theta[2] to urinary clearance, theta[3] to the generic uptake rate by PCs, theta[4] to the transfer rate of inactive PCs from the alveolar region to the tracheobronchial region, theta[5] to the transfer rate from the alveolar region to the lung interstitium, theta[6] to the transfer rate from the lung interstitium to the alveolar region, theta[7] to the uptake rate by PCs in the alveolar compartment, theta[8] to the uptake rate of PCs in the skeleton compartment, theta[9] to the partition coefficient of lungs, theta[10] to the partition coefficient of kidneys, theta[11] to the partition coefficient of brain, theta[12] to the partition coefficient of gonads, theta[13] to the partition coefficient of skin, theta[14] to the grouped partition coefficient of the soft tissues, heart and skeleton compartments and, finally, theta[15] to the grouped partition coefficient of the liver and spleen compartments.

Figure 17: Example of a chain traceplot illustrating the chains of the three errors, i.e., for the alveolar, tracheobronchial, lung interstitium and excreta compartments, for the spleen, heart, brain and uterus compartment, and for all the remaining compartments.

The posterior results give feedback for a future structural re-parameterisation. First of all, the unrealistically high partition coefficient of the lung compartment can be attributed to the low penetration of the ENMs through the air: blood barrier. An open question is whether the arithmetic values themselves or the ratio of the partition coefficient between the lungs and the rest of the tissues plays a more important role in the distribution of the substance. The high partition coefficient of the kidneys can be attributed to the drainage of ENMs towards the urine compartment, while for the uterus compartment, the model seemed unable to explain the experimental values and the statistical algorithm tried to compensate by increasing the partition coefficient. Regarding the higher maximum uptake capacity of the skeleton compartments, this can be due to the smaller total amount of tissue PCs found in literature. Finally, the ratio between the maximum uptake capacity of the alveolar PCs in relation to the PCs in the rest of the organs is probably indicative of the different behaviour of PCs in the first biolayer and after passing into systemic circulation.

There is room for improvement in the framework used for fitting the ODE system to the data. Firstly, parametric grouping could be more realistic, stemming from physiology and not from trial and error, as followed here, to achieve a better fit. Adding to that, a sensitivity analysis could reveal the most influential parameters and fit only those, while drawing the rest from literature. The statistical model could also be improved by using multivariate distributions that take into account the covariance of the parameters (Tsiros et al., 2019). Moreover, priors were not very objective but created after an initial fitting trial and error procedure, violating the Bayesian way of model fitting. This was mainly done due to very slow convergence. Finally, incorporation of more *in vivo* data would increase the trustworthiness of the model, decrease posterior uncertainty and expand the domain of applicability of the model (especially for the case of integration of data assessing different dose ranges).

7.2.5. Model validation

The validation of the model was performed via two routes: plotting curves that resulted using the mean estimates against the data and plotting visual predictive checks (VPC). Annex 5 includes the results of the first validation procedure, presenting 16 plots, one for each fitted compartment. The first 14 graphs comprise 5 curves, one for each group of animals. The reason behind this is that each group inhaled a slightly different amount of TiO₂ ENMs and it would be misleading to use a single mass-time profile to conclude about the goodness-of-fit of the model. The last 2 plots describe the mass-time profile of the ENMs in the excreta, and since only data from the 28 days group was used a single curve was plotted. All curves showed a satisfactory fit, especially taking into account that masses in many compartments differed by several orders of magnitude and the ODE system was very sensitive to changes in parameter values.

Annex 6 presents the visual predictive check (VPC) plots, which assess the impact of uncertainty in the posterior estimates. The circles represent the biodistribution data from all groups and the solid lines are the mean estimates. The colored ribbons were created by simulating 1,000 sets of 20 virtual rats, with exposure properties calculated by taking the mean of all exposure characteristics of the five groups. In each set, population means and variances were drawn from their posterior distribution. In each set, the 5th, 50th and 95th prediction percentiles were calculated and by ordering the percentiles produced by all 1,000 sets, the 95 % prediction interval (PI) was calculated for each of the three percentiles. Thus, the pink ribbon on the bottom of the VPC represents the 95 % CI of the 5th percentile of the model, the gray ribbon represents the 95 % CI of the 50th percentile of the model and finally the green ribbon depicts the 95 % CI of the 95th percentile of the model. From inspecting the plots it can be concluded that the posterior estimates include high uncertainty, but all experimental points fall within the prediction ribbons. Therefore, taking advantage of the variance of the posterior distributions would result in safer risk assessment and more reliable predictions.

7.2.6. Extrapolation of the TiO₂ PBPK model from rats to mice

One of the greatest advantages of PBPK models is their inherent ability to extrapolate a developed model from one organism to another, taking into account changes in physiology. This trait was exploited in this case since no mice biodistribution data that met the search criteria were available in literature. Thus, the approach adopted was to build a PBPK model using the available rat data and extrapolate the model to mice.

The first extrapolation stage included scaling the physiological parameters, namely regional blood flows, capillary and tissue volumes and total cardiac output from rats to mice, using information from Brown *et al.* (1997). Blood volume was mined from Sluiter *et al.* (1984) as a function of body weight, by averaging the slope of the linear models between Swiss male and female mice, as well as female B10 mice. The second stage utilised MPPD to calculate regional respiratory deposition fractions and respiratory clearance. Figures 18 to 21 present the input inserted into MPPD in order to run the model. Figures 22 and 23 present the clearance rates from the tracheobronchial and alveolar regions, which were combined and analysed using the same method as described in section 7.2.4. The resulting clearance was found to be 0.016 h⁻¹. The deposition fractions are presented in Figure 24. Finally, the

inhaled volume rate of the mouse, in L/min, was calculated from eq.4-4 of the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (1994) report describing methods for derivation of inhalation reference concentrations, using body weight as a predictor variable.

Figure 18: Mouse body weight inserted in MPPD.

Figure 19: Particle (ENM) properties inserted in MPPD.

Figure 20: Exposure scenario inserted in MPPD.

Figure 21: Clearance settings inserted in MPPD based on in vivo literature data for rats.

Figure 22: Mouse tracheobronchial clearance graph calculated using MPPD.

Figure 23: Mouse alveolar clearance graph calculated using MPPD.

Figure 24: Mouse deposition rates calculated using MPPD.

7.2.7. TiO_2 inhalation PBPK Jaqpot deployment

The PBPK model that was extrapolated from rats to mice was used to convert the external TiO_2 concentration produced by the GUIDEnano tool into an internal distribution. To achieve this, the PBPK model was deployed as a web service, using the R function described in section 4.2. The deployment process enabled communication with API calls, which were used to contact the PBPK and support it with the required input information. The input comprises the weight of the mouse, a vector containing the time-varying exposure concentration and the corresponding exposure time vector. The create.events function, described in section 4.2, takes the concentration vector and converts it into deposited mass for each of the three entrance compartments (alveolar, tracheobronchial and upper airways) for each provided time interval and then forces a change in the corresponding compartmental state variables; it adds the appropriate mass. The intervals are defined by a moving window across the time vector that records the difference between two consecutive time points, t_i and t_{i+1} . Then the deposited mass is found by adding the result of the multiplication of the concentration at the specific time window times the time interval times the inhalation volume rate times the deposition fraction to the corresponding state variable. Finally, the output of the model is the total mass in the lower respiratory system, namely the sum of the mass in the tracheobronchial region, alveolar region and lungs interstitium, over the time points generated by the end-user defined time sequence.

The TiO_2 ENM mouse inhalation PBPK web service consists of 3 main components: the 'Overview' tab, where the end-user can explore the details and specific features of the model, the 'Features' tab, where the end-user can investigate the dependent and independent features of the model, their definitions and units, and finally the 'Predict' tab, where the end-user can run simulations by providing different values for the input variables and witness the changes in the response, i.e. in the total lungs mass, either through inspecting the results in a tabular format, or by plotting them. These functionalities are illustrated in Figures 25 to 29.

Figure 25: Screenshot of the 'Overview' tab of the deterministic TiO₂ inhalation PBPK model uploaded on Jaqpot.

Figure 26: Screenshot of the 'Features' tab of the deterministic TiO₂ inhalation PBPK model uploaded on Jaqpot.

Figure 27: Screenshot of the 'Predict' tab of the deterministic TiO₂ inhalation PBPK model uploaded on Jaqpot.

Figure 28: Screenshot of the table-formatted mass-time profiles of the deterministic TiO₂ inhalation PBPK model uploaded on Jaqpot.

Figure 29: Screenshot of the generated plots of the deterministic TiO₂ ENM inhalation PBPK model uploaded on Jaqpot.

Two different TiO₂ ENM mouse inhalation PBPK models were uploaded on Jaqpot; one stochastic and one deterministic. The idea behind the deployment of two models was to serve the different needs of the end-users. If the goal is to obtain the expected value of the mass-time profile curve, then the deterministic model should be used. On the other hand, if the end-user wishes to explore the upper and lower bounds of the accumulated TiO₂ ENM, calling the stochastic model multiple times using the same input vector and then summarising the resulting mass distributions can meet this objective. Even if the stochastic model gives slightly different results for the same input values, it can be used for bootstrapping. In each call, the parameters of the ODEs are sampled from the posterior distributions that resulted from the fitting process described in section 7.2.4 and then an additive error is added to the final result, as calculated by the statistical model. It has to be highlighted that the error is additive and is considered independent of the dose level. The second model uses the mean parameter estimates, so it returns the same output vector for the same input vector.

The models can be accessed through the NanoCommons website via Jaqpot, and more specifically, the deterministic model can be found at <https://app.jaqpot.org/model/3xz9DIdtuIRw2qaj3kGf> and the stochastic model at <https://app.jaqpot.org/model/duWK41DfRR1nxFLHz1cK>. The R codes for model fitting, as well as plotting can be found in the NanoCommons github at: https://github.com/NanoCommons/TiO2_inhalation_PBPk.

7.3. AOP-based PODs

7.3.1. Updated Workflow description

The workflow consists of three consecutive parts, as previously described in Deliverable report 6.2. In D6.3, the workflow was updated using different modelling libraries for development of the predictive models and to perform the BMD analysis. We also included the additional parameter of time post exposure (p.e.). As described in D6.2, the normalized and log₂ transformed gene expression values, as well as the corresponding phenotypic and exposure information, were retrieved from the [GEO database](#), a public repository that archives and freely distributes a great amount of microarray, next-generation sequencing, and other forms of high-throughput functional genomic data. We focused only on the results for anatase TiO₂ ENMs with mean diameter of 20nm, since this was the material of interest for this case study. We also opted to use the complete dataset, taking into account datapoints for two different times describing the post exposure molecular phenomena. Indeed, for the first part, a full toxicogenomics analysis of the complete dataset was performed to identify the genes for which expression levels were affected by the exposure to each ENM. A list of the respective pathways was produced by projecting the differentially expressed gene lists to multiple pathway ontologies and databases. For the second part, we implemented BMD modeling on each affected gene extracted from the first part of the workflow and retrieved the lower limit of the BMD value. For the last part, we combined the results of the BMD modeling with prior knowledge collected in the form of KEGG pathways and AOPs.

The detailed presentation of the updated workflow follows next:

WORKFLOW Input: whole genome expression data

A. Toxicogenomics analysis using Bioinformatics

Note: Acute/subacute/chronic exposure related data can be included in the analysis depending on the phenotype of interest

- Input: publicly available data from the Gene Expression Omnibus (**GEO**) database, downloaded using the function `getGEO` of '**GEOquery**' R/Bioconductor library. The dataset includes the normalized, log₂ transformed relative intensities and the study design information.
- '**maanova**' library (Wu et al., 2003) for gene-wise Anova analysis and model development based on microarray experiments, using the dose, p.e. time and treatment as fixed effect independent variables, the set number as a random effects variable and the log₂ relative intensities as the dependent variable:
 - a. False discovery Rate (FDR) multiple testing correction at $\alpha = 0.05$
 - b. Gene selection criteria: $|\text{FoldChange (FC)}| > 0.5$ & F_s statistic to test for ENM

treatment effect result $F_s.Pvalperm < 0.05$ after performing 100 permutations. The permutation method was set to residual shuffling and was used to calculate the p values for all statistical tests. The false discovery rate (FDR) approach was applied to adjust for multiple comparisons.

- **Functional Pathway Analysis:** using Library 'enrichR' from R/Cran
- Output: **differentially expressed gene (DEG) lists** and the **corresponding affected pathways/functions** (one list for each ontology/database).

B. Pathway BMD response modelling:

- Input: ENM exposure doses ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mouse}$), the normalized \log_2 intensities
- The **BMDExpress2** (Philips et al., 2019) was used to perform the BMD analysis. (Version 2.30 BUILD 0488 with updated annotation files for GPL7202)
- Calculation of **Median pathway BMD** for which pathways gene sets were altered:
 - a. The \log_2 intensities corresponding to the common differentially expressed genes were centered using the mean of the control samples for each p.e. timepoint;
 - b. Model fitting using the BMDS EPA parametric models module was performed, setting a predefined Benchmark Dose Response (BMRr) = 10% for all available models. Gene set BMD/BMDL/BMDU were calculated in multiple ways including by median, mean and percentile. The output of the analysis was a collection of gene set BMD/BMDL/BMDU values that can be used to estimate biological potency;
 - c. A nested likelihood ratio test for the linear and polynomial models followed by an Akaike information criterion (AIC) that compares the best nested model to the exponential model, the Hill model and the power model was chosen for model selection;
 - d. Output: BMD/BMDL/BMDU for all available models and the respective model selection metric values for each gene at each p.e. timepoint, as well as a short list of the corresponding best models specifics;
 - e. The gene lists were then annotated and genes for which BMDL was out of the used ENM treatment range were excluded;
 - f. **Functional Pathway Analysis** using only the genes that have available BMD values: included pathways with at least 5 affected genes/probes for KEGG ontology:
 - i. Fisher's exact test was implemented to identify statistically significant ontology terms and the Benjamini & Hochberg (BH) method was used for multiple testing correction of the Fisher's exact p-values;
 - ii. Statistical significance threshold on (BH) adjusted p-values = 0.05.
 - g. Median BMDt was used to represent the gene set or pathway BMDt.

C. AOP-independent and AOP-dependent BMD analysis and grouping:

The median of the KEGG pathways that were most sensitive to ENM exposure was computed. Sensitivity was indicated by the respective pathway median BMDt value and was common to all ENMs groups, that have, most importantly, been associated with a **specific Adverse Outcome described by a specific MeSH term** and retrieved from the Comparative Toxicogenomics Database (CTD).

WORKFLOW Output: medianBMD_{ENM, t, AOP/KEGG} and the minimum of the most sensitive pathways
medianBMD_{ENM, t, AOP/KEGG}

We opted to focus on inhalation for this case study, as we did previously and reported in Deliverable Report D6.2. This is justified because inhalation is reported to be the most common and extensively investigated route of exposure to ENMs. A significant fraction of the inhaled ENMs can reach the distal regions of the lungs, which are more susceptible to the effects of the exposure due to the lack of the mucus that protects the tissues of the bronchial tree. Importantly, the alveolar ENM dose increases with exposure levels and persists for an extended period of time, even after ENM exposure has ceased, causing long-term damage to the lung cells (Kreyling, 2013). Upon inhalation, and according to Saber *et al.* (2013), most ENMs induce a dose-dependent increase in the levels of pro-inflammatory mediators (cytokines, chemokines, growth factors), acute phase response proteins, and an influx of pro-inflammatory cells in the bronchoalveolar lavage fluid resulting in lung inflammation. This flood of cells is associated with lung fibrosis, a pathological condition that has been reported in the past as an important result of ENM exposure in mice.

The global gene expression profiles that correspond to the lung exposure of mice at various doses were extracted for two timepoints: one shortly after the exposure (1 day p.e.) and the second after an extended clearance period (28 days p.e). The aim is to calculate realistic molecular Points of Departure (PoD) related to a specific Adverse Outcome in order to perform a precise and personalized Risk Assessment, and thus provide proof-of-concept to the paradigm shift in the field proposed by the National Research Council (NRC), (2007a, 2007b). For a comparison of the toxicogenomics to the traditional approaches, the reader can refer to the work of Moffat *et al.* (2015).

We have previously tried to answer the question of whether the short-term toxicogenomic profiles that are caused by the intratracheal exposure of mice to a variety of TiO₂ ENMs can be used to extract BMD values at gene or pathway level to successfully rank and/or group these ENMs by their potency to induce *in vivo* acute lung inflammation. Lung inflammation is a short-term local tissue response, which leads to the chronic medical condition of pulmonary fibrosis. The molecular events that eventually lead to the pathological phenotypes are described by AOP 173, ***“Substance interaction with the resident lung cell membrane components leading to lung fibrosis”*** [<https://aopwiki.org/aops/173>] (Figure 30).

This time, we focus on the short- and long-term effects of the exposure to a specific ENM: anatase TiO₂ 20nm, in relation to the manifestation of Lung Fibrosis. For more information about the ENM refer to section 7.1.1 of this Deliverable Report.

Figure 30: AOP 173 - Substance interaction with the resident lung cell membrane components leading to lung fibrosis.

Data corresponding to lung tissue samples from female C57BL/6 mice analyzed using Agilent mouse 4 × 44k oligonucleotide microarrays (Agilent Technologies Inc., Mississauga, ON, Canada) were used. The normalized and log₂ transformed gene expression values, and the corresponding phenotypic and exposure information, were retrieved from the [GEO database](#) (Edgar *et al.*, 2002, Barrett *et al.*, 2013). GSE81570 dataset was downloaded using the getGEO function of the GEOquery R/Bioconductor library (Davis & Meltzer, 2007). The R object that the getGEO function creates contains the series matrix that stores the log₂ transformed and Locally Weighted Scatterplot Smoothing (LOWESS) (Yang *et al.*, 2002) normalized gene expression values, together with the relevant information about all the samples that were analyzed and the experimental procedures utilised.

The complete dataset consists of samples that were extracted from 5–7 week old female C57BL/6 mice, exposed to anatase 20 nm TiO₂ ENMs. Control mice were only exposed to the vehicle, and thus received 40 µL of MilliQ water, while the ENM-exposed mice received 54, 162 or 486 µg/mouse doses of individual ENMs via a single intratracheal instillation. The information about the ENM characterization and the experimental procedure are provided in Rahman *et al.* (2017) while the preprocessing methodology is described in Nikota *et al.* (2016). Following removal of the data that correspond to one sample that lacked exposure information, the remaining 232 samples were processed. Detailed information for each analyzed sample is included in Annex 7.

The **ENM details (type, size(in nm))** column is included in the linear modelling as the independent variable of interest, and the **Dose µg/mouse** column and the **Time** were included as covariates as described below. The **Array** column was also included as a random effects covariate.

Table 7 contains the **LOWESS normalized, log₂ transformed intensities** for the first 8 samples and the first 20 probes included in the analysis. These measurements are the dependent variable in the linear model.

Table 7: Normalized log₂ transformed intensities (for the first 8 samples and 20 probes) based on data from 5–7 week old female C57BL/6 mice, exposed to anatase 20 nm TiO₂ ENMs.

PROBEID	GSM2157260	GSM2157261	GSM2157262	GSM2157263	GSM2157264	GSM2157265	GSM2157266	GSM2157267
A_51_P100021	0.029862525	-0.028325985	-0.005386312	-0.12772028	-0.10963171	-0.030885168	-0.041291486	-0.23467971
A_51_P100034	0.56587875	0.365373361	0.441949109	0.932538644	0.531856875	0.610567804	0.771338073	0.944475702
A_51_P100052	-0.143794802	-0.144276397	0.052947706	0.021560375	-0.182245818	-0.151358743	-0.202664434	0.133599593
A_51_P100063	0.992853322	0.812133294	0.757421914	0.714684217	1.046977235	0.706900483	1.223042656	1.15085269
A_51_P100084	0.204706629	-0.203780375	0.223592674	0.203276797	0.11015944	0.478794263	0.172800566	0.431406159
A_51_P100099	-0.35794919	0.039195371	-0.326068925	-0.363830538	-0.411238776	-0.132528514	-0.28513526	-0.588631447
A_51_P100155	-0.505203961	-0.443947587	-0.407879496	-0.335136964	-0.398636537	-0.513564458	-0.41328563	-0.353840162
A_51_P100174	-0.524461912	-0.482315368	0.016317949	-0.516455578	-0.186673633	-0.481854785	0.043488401	0.121645383
A_51_P100181	-0.239489666	-0.153954169	-0.376946222	-0.000146521	-0.312267172	-0.499504625	-0.073386756	-0.14267918
A_51_P100218	0.142534656	0.138327105	-0.110055878	-0.074413341	-0.140603594	0.067142395	-0.025926188	0.095902221
A_51_P100227	-1.660637029	-1.712244881	-0.791952208	-1.62311488	-2.018268873	-1.763684463	-1.54622705	-1.710410612
A_51_P100238	-0.019028984	-0.139422683	-0.002379886	-0.007773999	-0.182329713	-0.082383273	0.031866691	-0.088999459
A_51_P100246	-0.468215574	-0.559547065	-0.43651828	-0.019439661	-0.504550976	-0.74964601	-0.788461064	-0.953671795
A_51_P100289	0.164925864	0.181261719	-0.120088622	0.267852168	-0.04540778	0.021468864	0.215071187	0.531130417
A_51_P100298	0.448485053	0.507155114	0.261992965	0.705507818	0.60687037	0.559881726	0.446137402	0.525607904
A_51_P100309	0.040025186	0.086122326	-0.130569919	0.023394068	0.062860557	0.146161326	-0.056981643	-0.038428251
A_51_P100327	0.000766082	0.257920859	0.226554453	-0.150214799	0.153619147	0.302199207	-0.058430823	-0.328864162
A_51_P100347	-0.343633844	-0.385375311	-0.23314758	-0.118447989	-0.080908253	-0.233639094	-0.039392716	-0.113901649
A_51_P100379	0.04969412	0.050466582	0.075097864	0.169511267	-0.04838839	0.173707991	0.103780484	-0.118625044
A_51_P100428	-0.117112598	-0.096537885	-0.01905053	-0.024128739	-0.226096905	-0.087650913	0.179144979	-0.078316017

The corresponding linear models were developed using the ‘maanova’ R/Bioconductor package and had the following structure:

$$Y_i \sim a + b_1 X_i + b_2 D_i + b_3 t_i$$

where

Y_i : is the measurement, here the **normalized, log2 transformed intensity** for gene i

a : is the intercept of the model

X_i : is the **exposure** of interest

D_i : is the **respective dose** of the exposure of interest

t_i : is the **respective time point** of the exposure of interest

The F_s statistic was used to test for the ENM exposure effects. The permutation method used was residual shuffling and the FDR method described by Storey (2002) was used to correct for multiple testing. Genes showing expression changes of at least 0.5-fold in either direction and FDR corrected p-values smaller than 0.005 were considered as significantly DEGs and used in the downstream analyses (Table 8 presents the first 20 DEGs).

Table 8: The annotated differentially expressed gene list for the 20 first results from the Anova analysis of the data in Table 7.

PROBEID	Fold.change	F1.Pvalperm	Fs.Pvalperm	ENSEMBL	ENTREZID	GENENAME	SYMBOL
A_51_P104933	0.731664889	0.000482767	0.000463207	ENSMUSG00000039826	227682	TruB pseudouridine (psi) synthase family member 2	Trub2
A_51_P105078	0.510595535	0.042807693	0.038940817	ENSMUSG00000001020	20198	S100 calcium binding protein A4	S100a4
A_51_P112966	0.906628591	0.016251371	0.0170545	ENSMUSG00000050370	12642	cholesterol 25-hydroxylase	Ch25h
A_51_P114462	0.895278884	0.008239339	0.007304626	ENSMUSG00000031780	20295	chemokine (C-C motif) ligand 17	Ccl17
A_51_P114634	0.560210649	0.009830187	0.009209021	ENSMUSG00000050022	231842	archaelysin family metalloproteinase 1	Amz1
A_51_P120295	0.8211044	0.000458465	0.000390303	ENSMUSG00000022445	76279	cytochrome P450, family 2, subfamily d, polypeptide 26	Cyp2d26
A_51_P122321	0.621093256	0.008759743	0.007919272	ENSMUSG00000024810	77125	interleukin 33	Il33
A_51_P123625	1.514719781	0.012356637	0.010844323	ENSMUSG00000022126	16365	aconitate decarboxylase 1	Acod1
A_51_P123630	1.394904465	0.015585158	0.014531903	ENSMUSG00000022126	16365	aconitate decarboxylase 1	Acod1
A_51_P124133	0.624229139	0.011743176	0.011166168	ENSMUSG00000068086	13105	cytochrome P450, family 2, subfamily d, polypeptide 9	Cyp2d9
A_51_P124315	0.754702257	0.020315028	0.018610675	ENSMUSG00000055632	665700	hemicentin 2	Hmcn2
A_51_P125205	0.58282756	0.0190724	0.017586166	ENSMUSG00000004655	11826	aquaporin 1	Aqp1

A_51_P127456	0.73959535	0.004137747	0.003622085	ENSMUSG00000051403	232947	protein phosphatase 1, regulatory subunit 37	Ppp1r37
A_51_P128973	0.726587491	0.001398216	0.001293602	ENSMUSG00000005681	11807	apolipoprotein A-II	Apoa2
A_51_P129006	0.736599258	0.030477432	0.032688854	ENSMUSG00000060802	12010	beta-2 microglobulin	B2m
A_51_P131084	0.517213001	0.026801114	0.029570281	ENSMUSG00000032314	110842	electron transferring flavoprotein, alpha polypeptide	Etfa
A_51_P134142	0.548462252	0.001296269	0.001210325	ENSMUSG00000060613	226105	cytochrome P450, family 2, subfamily c, polypeptide 70	Cyp2c70
A_51_P136521	0.835641458	0.038707287	0.034584062	ENSMUSG00000022595	68311	Ly6/Plaur domain containing 2	Lypd2
A_51_P139678	1.106136214	0.047913049	0.04212696	ENSMUSG00000050359	20753	small proline-rich protein 1A	Sprr1a

We then proceeded with the Functional Pathway Analysis (also known as Gene Set Enrichment Analysis) (Subramanian *et al.*, 2005), using the ‘enrichR’ R/Cran package (Chen *et al.*, 2013, Kuleshov *et al.*, 2016). The anova DEGs list was used as input and we thus retrieved lists of significantly altered (‘biological process’) GO terms (Ashburner *et al.*, 2000), mouse KEGG pathways (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2016) and mouse Wikipathways (Kelder *et al.*, 2012, Martens *et al.*, 2018, Pico *et al.*, 2008).

For the pathway BMD response modelling, the normalized gene expression data were analyzed using BMDExpress2 software (Version 2.30 BUILD 0488 released on June 9, 2020 using the last updated version of the annotation files for GPL7202). We used as input the normalized log₂ intensities for the Anova retrieved DEGs which were centered using the mean of the respective control sample values before they were imported into BMDExpress2. This software implements a nested likelihood ratio test for the linear and polynomial models followed by an AIC that compares the best nested model to the exponential model, the Hill model and the power model in order to provide the best model fit.

Subsequently, we filtered out the probes for which BMD values were not available, or where the respective BMDL value was negative or greater than the highest ENM dose administered and projected them onto KEGG pathways and Wikipathways ontologies using the ‘enrichR’ R/Cran library. Functional Pathway Analysis outputs are the sets of significantly enriched ontology terms. The statistically significant perturbed terms that were represented with more than 4 genes in our dataset are listed in Table 9. The barplots of the most significantly perturbed pathways retrieved by this part of the analysis are depicted in Figure 31. An overlap of the affected biological mechanisms identified by using both ontologies is obvious. Importantly, the Lung Fibrosis Wikipathway (WP 36632) is included in the significantly affected pathways |

Table 9: Functional analysis results for the DEGs for which BMDt values are available (only terms with at least 5 affected genes from the ENM exposure were included here).

Ontology	Term	Overlap	P.value	Odds Ratio	Combined Score	Genes	Genes Count
KEGG Pathways	PPAR signaling pathway	8/85	4.10E-06	8.634646519	107.1013746	SLC27A1;ACOX1;ME1;APOA2;APOA1;LPL;APOC3;APOA5	8
	Chemokine signaling pathway	8/197	0.001470801	3.725608904	24.29822764	CCL7;STAT1;STAT2;CCL4;CCL2;CXCL1;CCL17;CXCL5	8
	Herpes simplex virus 1 infection	8/433	0.102310343	1.695022989	3.864219339	H2-T22;H2-Q8;STAT1;OAS2;STAT2;OAS1A;CCL2;B2M	8
	Cholesterol metabolism	7/49	9.67E-07	13.1061599	181.5122282	APOH;APOA2;APOA1;LPL;APOC3;APOE;ABCB11	7
	Epstein-Barr virus infection	7/229	0.01301271	2.804374825	12.17611522	H2-T22;H2-Q8;STAT1;OAS2;STAT2;OAS1A;B2M	7
	Cytokine-cytokine receptor interaction	7/292	0.041433466	2.199321352	7.001905419	IL33;CCL7;CCL4;CCL2;CXCL1;CCL17;CXCL5	7
	Pathways in cancer	7/535	0.366098169	1.200377261	1.206203606	STAT1;STAT2;MGST1;CKS2;PDGFA;F2;KNG1	7
	IL-17 signaling pathway	6/91	0.000482821	6.048996875	46.18931475	CCL7;LCN2;CCL2;CXCL1;CCL17;CXCL5	6
	Retinol metabolism	6/91	0.000482821	6.048996875	46.18931475	CYP26B1;CYP3A41A;CYP2S1;CYP2C40;CYP2C70;ADH7	6
Influenza A	6/168	0.010386128	3.276539974	14.9648892	IL33;OAS2;STAT1;STAT2;OAS1A;CCL2	6	
Wikipathways	Complement and Coagulation Cascades WP449	9/62	2.26E-08	13.31754957	234.4386603	FGB;C4BP;F9;CFH;SERPINC1;SERPINE1;F2;F3;KNG1	9
	PPAR signaling pathway WP2316	8/81	2.85E-06	9.061048816	115.7034397	SLC27A1;ACOX1;ME1;APOA2;APOA1;LPL;APOC3;APOA5	8

Chemokine signaling pathway WP2292	8/190	1.17E-03	3.86286818	26.08301049	CCL7;STAT1;STAT2;CCL4;CCL2;CXCL1;CCL17;CXCL5	8
Lung fibrosis WP3632	6/61	5.27E-05	9.02391337	88.88870021	CCL4;SPP1;PDGFA;CCL2;MT2;TIMP1	6
Adipogenesis genes WP447	6/134	0.0035359403 13	4.107900863	23.18818026	SFRP4;CYP26B1;STAT1;STAT2;SERPINE1;LPL	6
mRNA processing WP310	6/457	3.81E-01	1.204504848	1.163341914	SF3B4;RBM3;NPM1;TAF15;OAS2;OAS1A	6
Blood Clotting Cascade WP460	5/20	1.99E-06	22.93577982	301.0420588	FGB;F9;FGG;SERPINE1;F2	5

A. KEGG pathways

B. Wikipathways

Figure 31: Barplots of the Functional Analysis results for the DEGs that BMDt values were successfully calculated. The colour of the bars is brighter with lower p-value.

In the next step, the BMDt values corresponding to the genes associated with each ontology term were extracted. The KEGG pathways that have been associated with the specific AOP of interest (Lung Fibrosis - AOP 173) were retrieved from CTD using the 'CTDquerier' R/Bioconductor package (Davis *et al.*, 2019, Hernandez-Ferrer & Gonzalez, 2018) and 'Pulmonary Fibrosis' (MESH:D011658) as the query term. Two KEGG pathways, namely Influenza A and Epstein-Barr virus infection were excluded, because they cannot be associated with toxicity induced lung fibrosis. The median BMDt value of the associated genes for each term was calculated. Table 10 contains the median BMDt values for each Lung Fibrosis associated KEGG pathway and the median of all pathways for anatase TiO₂ ENM with diameter 20 nm.

Table 10: Median BMDt values (μg) for the AOP associated KEGG pathways 1 day and 28 days post exposure (p.e.) for anatase TiO₂ with diameter 20 nm.

Lung Fibrosis associated KEGG pathway	Median pathway BMDt (1d p.e)	Median pathway BMDt (28d p.e.)
IL-17 signaling pathway	0.000098	371.804
Cytokine-cytokine receptor interaction	0.041	247.069
Chemokine signaling pathway	29.265	432.099
NOD-like receptor signaling pathway	221.575	432.099
PPAR signaling pathway	260.605	295.682
Pathways in cancer	281.778	328.979
AOPmedianBMDt	125.42	350.392

The complete workflow, that has been implemented in R 3.6.3, is available at the following link: https://github.com/nanocommons/aop_bmdt_nanocommons.

8. Web Implementation of the risk assessment - decision support workflow

8.1 Implementation of the code

The GUI of the application was developed using the [ZK platform](#), which is an open-source Java framework. The application integrates exposure scenario results from the GUIDEnano tool, the PBPK model developed in the Jaqpot platform and the BMDt values on lung fibrosis AOP, which were computed using the omics analysis workflow presented in Section 7.3. The web application is hosted and implemented within the [Enalos Cloud Platform](#) and can be accessed via the following link:

<http://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/nanocommons/exposure/>

The full Graphical User Interface (GUI) can be seen in Figure 32 below and includes on the top an outline of the overall workflow and short descriptions of the external and internal exposure simulation tools and the risk assessment method, as performed within the application.

NanoCommons Risk Assessment Tool

Short description
The workflow is a combination of nano-informatics tools available through the NanoCommons computational infrastructure. This web application, hosted and implemented within [Enalos Cloud Platform](#), estimates the risk of triggering AOP-173 (Lung Fibrosis) in mice due to exposure to 20nm TiO₂ engineered nanoparticles.

External exposure: Four different exposure scenarios have been simulated using the [GUIDEnano tool](#). The user can alternatively enter a custom-made scenario.

Case 1
45 g (initial mass 3000 kg) of TiO₂ (22nm) poured over 7 hours in the NF, with 1 min activity duration every hour. For every hour the mouse stays 90 s in the NF and spends the rest of the time in the FF.

Internal exposure: Concentration-time profiles for mice are simulated using a PBPK model which has been developed and implemented in the [Jaqpot platform](#). A plot depicting the mass-time profile in the lung is automatically generated.

Weight (5 - 50 grams)

Risk assessment: is performed by comparing the predicted distribution of TiO₂ concentration with Points of Departure (POD) that have been computed using a [gene expression analysis tool](#). The user can select the POD of interest among different pathways involved in AOP-173 or the median defines the POD of the AOP and short term (1 day) or long term (28 days) effects.

Pathways: IL-17 signaling pathway
Time: Median pathway BMDt (1d p.e.)
 logarithmic scale

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Figure 32: GUI for NanoCommons Risk Assessment Tool

The user can interact with the application by either defining a custom-made external exposure scenario or by selecting one of the predefined case studies, described in detail in Section 7.1.5, which are available through the application. A short description of the case studies is provided next, for completeness of this section:

Case 1: 45 g (initial mass 3,000 kg) of TiO₂ (22nm) poured over 7 hours in the NF, with 1 min activity duration every hour. The mouse stays 90 s in the NF and spends the rest of the time in the FF.

Case 2: 30 g (initial mass 2000 kg) of TiO₂ (22nm) poured over 7 hours in the NF, with 1 min activity duration every hour. The mouse stays 90 s in the NF and spends the rest of the time in the FF.

Case 3: 7.5 g (initial mass 500 kg) of TiO₂ (22nm) poured over 7 hours in the NF, with 1 min activity duration every hour. The mouse stays 90 s in the NF and spends the rest of the time in the FF.

Case 4: 2.6 g (initial mass 175 kg) of TiO₂ (22nm) poured over 7 hours in the NF, with 1 min activity duration every hour. The mouse stays 90 s in the NF and spends the rest of the time in the FF.

The case studies are stored in a database and are retrieved through GET type Representational state transfer (REST) APIs. REST API is an architectural style that defines how applications communicate over the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP). This architectural design ensures fast and efficient transfer of the relevant information. Furthermore, it facilitates the easy incorporation of new cases into the database, so that they are immediately available in the web app and simplifies the deployment of the application to any server without having to provide each time a new database.

For defining a custom-made scenario, the user needs to upload a data file containing the concentration of the ENM as a function of time, in a discrete time series form. A template can be downloaded to assist the user to prepare the data file in a specific format that is accepted by the web application.

A snapshot of the GUI, where the user can select the exposure scenario, is shown in Figure 33 along with the available choices. A graph showing micrograms of TiO₂ ENM released versus the exposure time is automatically plotted on the right part of the screen. The user is able to download the timeseries of the selected case study.

Figure 33: GUI section for selecting the external exposure scenario.

In the next step, the user defines the weight of the mouse that is exposed to the specific NM external exposure scenario (Figure 34). Once this input is provided, the system is ready to compute the Internal Exposure in the mouse. The user presses the “Compute” button and the GUI calls and simulates the PBPK model and calculates the concentration-time profiles for mice. A plot depicting the concentration-time profile in the lung is automatically generated.

Figure 34: GUI section for defining the weight of the mouse.

When the PBPK simulation is completed, risk assessment is performed by comparing the predicted distribution of TiO₂ ENM concentration in the mouse lungs with Points of Departure (POD) that have been computed using a gene expression analysis workflow. The user can select the POD of interest among different pathways involved in AOP 173 (lung fibrosis) or the median value that defines the POD of the AOP and short term (1 day) or long term (28 days) effects.

For the POD, nine selections are available as shown below:

1. IL-17 signaling pathway
2. Cytokine-cytokine receptor interaction
3. Chemokine signaling pathway
4. NOD-like receptor signaling pathway
5. PPAR signaling pathway
6. Pathways in cancer
7. AOPmedianBMDt

A snapshot of the Risk Assessment section, along with the available selections for the Pathways (short-term or long-term effects) can be seen in Figure 35. The user has the option to plot the results on the logarithmic scale.

Risk assessment: Is performed by comparing the predicted distribution of TiO₂ concentration in the lungs with Points of Departure (POD) that have been computed using a [gene expression analysis workflow](#). The user can select the POD of interest among different pathways involved in AOP173 or the median value that defines the POD of the AOP and short term (1 day) or long term (28 days) effects.

The figure displays two screenshots of the Risk Assessment section of the GUI. Both screenshots feature a 'Pathways' dropdown menu and a 'Time' dropdown menu, along with a 'logarithmic scale' checkbox.

Top Screenshot:

- Pathways:** IL-17 signaling pathway (selected)
- Time:** (empty)
- logarithmic scale:**
- Dropdown Menu (Pathways):**
 - IL-17 signaling pathway
 - Cytokine-cytokine receptor interaction
 - Chemokine signaling pathway
 - NOD-like receptor signaling pathway
 - PPAR signaling pathway
 - Pathways in cancer
 - AOPmedianBMDt

Bottom Screenshot:

- Pathways:** IL-17 signaling pathway
- Time:** Median pathway BMDt (1d p.e) (selected)
- logarithmic scale:**
- Dropdown Menu (Time):**
 - Median pathway BMDt (1d p.e)
 - Median pathway BMDt (28d p.e)

Figure 35: The Risk Assessment section of the GUI.

8.2 Results

This section presents the results in the specific risk assessment scenarios. In the first scenario, a mouse

with a weight of 30 g is exposed to the external exposure scenario defined by case study 1. The simulated accumulation of TiO₂ ENM in the lungs as a function of time is presented in Figure 36. The predicted TiO₂ ENM concentration in the lungs at the 8th hour, in the form of a probability density function (PDF) (black curve), is compared with the BMDt value corresponding to the IL-17 signaling pathway and 1d p.e. (red line) in Figure 37. The results show that it is highly likely that in this particular scenario, the IL-17 signaling pathway will be activated because the BMDt value is much lower compared to the concentration of the ENM in the lungs. The plots depicted in Figures 36 and 37 are produced automatically by the web application.

Figure 36: Accumulation of TiO₂ ENMs in the lungs of a mouse weighting 30 gr in Case Study 1.

Figure 37: Probability density function of concentration in the lungs (black curve) and BMDt value (red line) for Case 1, with a mouse weighting 30 gr, IL-17 signaling pathway, 1d p.e.

In the second scenario, a mouse with a weight of 30 g is exposed to the external exposure scenario defined by case study 3. The simulated accumulation of TiO₂ ENM in the lungs as a function of time is

presented in Figure 38. The predicted TiO₂ ENM concentration in the lungs at the 8th hour, in the form of a probability density function (PDF) (black line), is compared with the BMDt value corresponding to the NOD-like receptor signalling pathway and 1d p.e. (red line) in Figure 39. The results show that now it is highly unlikely that the NOD-like receptor signalling pathway will be activated because the BMDt value is much higher compared to the concentration of the ENM in the lungs.

Figure 39. Figure 38: Accumulation of ENM in the lungs of a mouse weighting 30 gr in Case Study 3.

Figure 39: Probability density function of TiO₂ ENM concentration in the lungs (black curve) and BMDt value (red line) for Case 3, mouse weighting 30 gr, NOD-like receptor signalling pathway, 1d p.e.

9. Conclusions

Within WP6, NanoCommons has proposed a novel risk assessment workflow that introduces the concepts of personalised RA and also RA at the level of AOP, i.e., estimation of the probability of triggering a particular AOP. This concept requires the scientific interconnection of various modelling approaches, including exposure, biokinetics and omics analysis methodologies. In deliverable D6.3 we have demonstrated that this integration is not only scientifically, but also technically, feasible. The state-of-the-art technologies that are used for developing the NanoCommons computational services allow the seamless integration of the tools and the creation of novel computational workflows and user-friendly outputs.

A limitation in the implementation of the decision support integrated RA workflow was the lack of experimental data that restricted the domain on which this RA concept can be applied. Gene expression data were only available for mice, while the exposure data was available for rats and needed to be extrapolated for mice, and this limitation drove the approach used to complete the case study. However, the different tools comprising the workflow and the complete application can be easily adjusted to other case studies, provided that the required experimental data are available.

The NanoCommons RA concept and tool provide many new functionalities to the interested stakeholders, including risk assessors and environmental health and safety practitioners. By introducing AOPs into the RA workflow, risks can now be associated with the probability of triggering an MIE instead of the final adverse effect, which is the current practice. In addition, protective measures and manufacturing procedures and practices can be tailored to the specific characteristics of each individual worker, resembling the ideas of personalised medical treatment.

Also, the tool developed and demonstrated in Deliverable D6.3 can be considered as the basis for developing an Integrated Approach to Testing and Assessment system, which can be extended to environmental RA by integrating environmental exposure models with biokinetics models for species of interest like fish enriched by following alternative hazard assessment routes in the overall workflow depicted in Figure 1.

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Annex

Annex 3: Example of deploy.pbpk() usage

```
user_input <-list("weight" = 250,"dose" = c(10,12), "administration.time" = c(0,1.5) )
```

```
predicted.feats <- c("Li")
```

```
#####
```

```
# Function for creating parameter vector #
```

```
#####
```

```
create.params <- function(input){
```

```
  with( as.list(input),{
```

```
#####
```

```
# Physiological parameters #
```

```
#####
```

```
# tissue weights (in g)
```

```

W_tot <- weight # ;body weight, experimental data - g
W_lu <-1.2 # weight of lungs, experimental data - g
W_li <- 10.03 # weight of liver, experimental data - g

W_blood <- 0.065 * W_tot
W_rob <- W_tot - (W_blood + W_li + W_lu)

#Regional blood flows (in mL per hour)
fQl = 0.183 # fraction of cardiac output to liver, literature (chapter 5) - unitless
fQrob = 1-fQl # fraction of cardiac output to rest of the body, fitted value - unitless
Q_tot <- 4980 # cardiac output, literature (chapter 5) - mL/h
Q_li <- fQl*Q_tot # blood flow to liver - mL/h
Q_rob <- fQrob*Q_tot # blood flow to rest of the body - mL/h

P <-1.435445 # partition coefficient tissue:blood, fitted value - unitless
CLE_f <- 9.958839e-05 # clearance rate to feces from liver, fitted value - mL/h

return(list("W_lu" = W_lu, "W_li" = W_li, "W_rob" = W_rob, "W_blood" = W_blood, "Q_tot" = Q_tot,
           "Q_li" = Q_li, "Q_rob" = Q_rob, "P" = P, "CLE_f" = CLE_f, "dose" = dose))
})
}

### store the values
params <- create.params(user_input)

#####
# Function for creating initial values for ODEs #
#####

create.inits <- function(parameters){
  with( as.list(parameters),{
    Lu <- 0; Rob <- 0; Li <- 0; Art_blood <- 0; Ven_blood <- 0;

```

```
        return(c("Lu" = Lu, "Rob" = Rob, "Li" = Li, "Art_blood" = Art_blood,
               "Ven_blood" = Ven_blood))
    })
}

##store the values
inits <- create.inits(params)

#####

# Function for creating events #
#####

create.events<- function(parameters){
  with( as.list(parameters),{

        Idose <- length(dose)
        ltimes <- length(administration.time)

        addition <- dose
        if (ltimes == Idose){
          events <- list(data = rbind(data.frame(var = "Ven_blood", time = administration.time,
                                                value = addition, method = c("add"))) )
        }else{
          stop("The times when the drug is injected should be equal in number to the doses")
        }

        return(events)
    })
}

events <- create.events(params)
```

```
#####  
# Custom function #  
#####  
custom.func <- function(W_li){  
  if (W_li<15){  
    a = 10  
  }else{  
    a = 15  
  }  
  return(a)  
}  
  
#####  
# ODEs system #  
#####  
  
ode.func <- function(time, Initial.values, Parameters, custom.func){  
  with( as.list(c(Initial.values, Parameters)),{  
  
    #clearance coefficient  
    cl = custom.func(weight)  
    # concentrations in tissues  
    C_lu <- Lu/W_lu  
    C_re <- Rob/W_re  
    C_li <- Li_tissue/W_li  
    C_art <- Art_blood/(0.2*W_blood)  
    C_ven <- Ven_blood/(0.8*W_blood)  
  
    # Lungs  
    dlu <- Q_tot * (C_ven - C_lu/P)  
    # Rest of the body  
    dRob_tissue <- Q_rob * (C_art - C_rob/P)
```

```
# Liver
dLi_tissue <- Q_li * (C_art - C_li/P) - CLE*cl*C_li
# Arterial blood
dArt_blood <- Q_tot* C_lu/P - Cart * (Q_li + Q_rob)
# Venous blood
dVen_blood <- Q_li*C_li/P + Q_rob*C_rob/P - Q_tot * C_ven
list(c(dLu = dLu, dRob = dRob, dLi = dLi, dArt_blood = dArt_blood, dVen_blood = dVen_blood)
})
}

deploy.pbpk(user.input, predicted.feats, create.params, create.inits, create.events, custom.func,
ode.func, method = "bdf", list(rtol=1e-07, atol=1e-09)
```

Annex 2: Output from the GUIDEnano Tool

Figure A2.1: Particle concentration in mass per m^3 over time in the Near Field (NF) for case study 1.

Figure A2.2: Particle concentration in mass per m^3 over time in the Far Field (FF) for case study 1.

Figure A2.3: Particle concentration in mass per m^3 over time in the FF for case study 2.

Figure A2.4: Particle concentration in mass per m^3 over time in the NF for case study 2.

Figure A2.5: Particle concentration in mass per m^3 over time in the Far Field for case study 3.

Figure A2.6: Particle concentration in mass per m^3 over time in the NF for case study 3.

Figure A2.7: Particle concentration in mass per m^3 over time in the FF for case study 4.

Figure A2.8: Particle concentration in mass per m^3 over time in the NF for case study 4.

Annex 3: Combined Scenarios

Figure A3.1: Combined concentration-time profile for case study 1.

Figure A3.2: Combined concentration-time profile for case study 2.

Figure A3.3: Combined concentration-time profile for case study 3.

Figure A3.4: Combined concentration-time profile for case study 4.

Annex 4: PBPK structural model (ODEs system and parameter definition)

Upper airways

$$\frac{dM_{ua}}{dt} = -(k_{ua-br} \cdot M_{ua}) - (CLE_{ua} \cdot M_{ua}) + IVR \cdot EC \cdot D_{ua}$$

Tracheobronchial region

$$\frac{dM_{tb}}{dt} = (k_{al-pc-tb} \cdot M_{al-pc}) - (CLE_{muc} \cdot M_{tb}) + IVR \cdot EC \cdot D_{tb}$$

Alveolar region region

$$\frac{dM_{al}}{dt} = (k_{lu-al} \cdot M_{lu-tis}) - (k_{al-lu} \cdot M_{al}) - (M_{al} \cdot kalab) - M_{al-pc} \cdot k_{de} + IVR \cdot EC \cdot D_{al}$$

$$\frac{dM_{al-pc}}{dt} = (M_{al} \cdot kalab - M_{al} \cdot k_{de}) - (k_{al-pc-tb} \cdot M_{al-pc})$$

Lungs

$$\frac{dM_{lu-cap}}{dt} = C_{ven} \cdot Q_{lu} - C_{lu-cap} \cdot Q_{lu} + \frac{x_{lu} \cdot Q_{lu} \cdot C_{lu-tis}}{P_{lu}} - x_{lu} \cdot Q_{lu} \cdot C_{lu-cap}$$

$$\frac{dM_{lu-tis}}{dt} = -\frac{x_{lu} \cdot Q_{lu} \cdot C_{lu-tis}}{P_{lu}} + x_{lu} \cdot Q_{lu} \cdot C_{lu-cap} - V_{lu-tis} \cdot C_{lu} \cdot k_{luab} - M_{lu-pc} \cdot k_{de}$$

$$\frac{dM_{lu-pc}}{dt} = V_{lu-tis} \cdot C_{lu} \cdot k_{luab} - M_{lu-pc} \cdot k_{de}$$

Liver

$$\frac{dM_{li-cap}}{dt} = C_{art} \cdot Q_{li} + C_{spl-cap} \cdot Q_{spl} - C_{li-cap} \cdot (Q_{li} + Q_{spl}) + \frac{x \cdot Q_{li} \cdot C_{li-tis}}{P} - x_{li} \cdot Q_{li} \cdot C_{li-cap}$$

$$\frac{dM_{li-tis}}{dt} = -\frac{x \cdot Q_{li} \cdot C_{li-tis}}{P} + x \cdot Q_{li} \cdot C_{li-cap} - V_{li-tis} \cdot C_{li} \cdot k_{liab} - M_{li-pc} \cdot k_{de} - CLE_{hep} \cdot M_{li-tis}$$

$$\frac{dM_{li-pc}}{dt} = V_{li-tis} \cdot C_{li} \cdot k_{liab} - M_{li-pc} \cdot k_{de}$$

Spleen

$$\frac{dM_{spl-cap}}{dt} = C_{art} \cdot Q_{spl} - C_{spl-cap} \cdot Q_{spl} + \frac{x \cdot Q_{spl} \cdot C_{spl-tis}}{P} - x \cdot Q_{spl} \cdot C_{spl-cap}$$

$$\frac{dM_{spl-tis}}{dt} = -\frac{x \cdot Q_{spl} \cdot C_{spl-tis}}{P} + x \cdot Q_{spl} \cdot C_{spl-cap} - V_{spl-tis} \cdot C_{spl} \cdot k_{splab} - M_{spl-pc} \cdot k_{de}$$

$$\frac{dM_{spl-pc}}{dt} = V_{spl-tis} \cdot C_{spl} \cdot k_{splab} - M_{spl-pc} \cdot k_{de}$$

Kidneys

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dM_{ki_cap}}{dt} &= C_{art} \cdot Q_{ki} - C_{ki_cap} \cdot Q_{ki} + \frac{x \cdot Q_{ki} \cdot C_{ki_tis}}{P_{ki}} - x \cdot Q_{ki} \cdot C_{ki_cap} - CLE_{ur} \cdot M_{ki_cap} \\ \frac{dM_{ki_tis}}{dt} &= -\frac{x \cdot Q_{ki} \cdot C_{ki_tis}}{P_{ki}} + x \cdot Q_{ki} \cdot C_{ki_cap} - V_{ki_tis} \cdot C_{ki} \cdot kkiab - M_{ki_pc} \cdot k_{de} \\ \frac{dM_{ki_pc}}{dt} &= V_{ki_tis} \cdot C_{ki} \cdot kkiab - M_{ki_pc} \cdot k_{de}\end{aligned}$$

Heart

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dM_{ht_cap}}{dt} &= C_{art} \cdot Q_{ht} - C_{ht_cap} \cdot Q_{ht} + \frac{x \cdot Q_{ht} \cdot C_{ht_tis}}{P_{ht}} - x \cdot Q_{ht} \cdot C_{ht_cap} \\ \frac{dM_{ht_tis}}{dt} &= -\frac{x \cdot Q_{ht} \cdot C_{ht_tis}}{P_{ht}} + x \cdot Q_{ht} \cdot C_{ht_cap} - V_{ht_tis} \cdot C_{ht} \cdot khtab - M_{ht_pc} \cdot k_{de} \\ \frac{dM_{ht_pc}}{dt} &= V_{ht_tis} \cdot C_{ht} \cdot khtab - M_{ht_pc} \cdot k_{de}\end{aligned}$$

Brain

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dM_{br_cap}}{dt} &= C_{art} \cdot Q_{br} - C_{br_cap} \cdot Q_{br} + \frac{x_{br} \cdot Q_{br} \cdot C_{br_tis}}{P_{br}} - x_{br} \cdot Q_{br} \cdot C_{br_cap} \\ \frac{dM_{br_tis}}{dt} &= -\frac{x_{br} \cdot Q_{br} \cdot C_{br_tis}}{P_{br}} + x_{br} \cdot Q_{br} \cdot C_{br_cap} - V_{br_tis} \cdot C_{br} \cdot kbrab - M_{br_pc} \cdot k_{de} \\ \frac{dM_{br_pc}}{dt} &= V_{br_tis} \cdot C_{br} \cdot kbrab - M_{br_pc} \cdot k_{de}\end{aligned}$$

Uterus

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dM_{ut_cap}}{dt} &= C_{art} \cdot Q_{ut} - C_{ut_cap} \cdot Q_{ut} + \frac{x \cdot Q_{ut} \cdot C_{ut_tis}}{P_{ut}} - x \cdot Q_{ut} \cdot C_{ut_cap} \\ \frac{dM_{ut_tis}}{dt} &= -\frac{x \cdot Q_{ut} \cdot C_{ut_tis}}{P_{ut}} + x \cdot Q_{ut} \cdot C_{ut_cap} - V_{ut_tis} \cdot C_{ut} \cdot kutab - M_{ut_pc} \cdot k_{de} \\ \frac{dM_{ut_pc}}{dt} &= V_{ut_tis} \cdot C_{ut} \cdot kutab - M_{ut_pc} \cdot k_{de}\end{aligned}$$

Skeleton

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dM_{skel_cap}}{dt} &= C_{art} \cdot Q_{skel} - C_{skel_cap} \cdot Q_{skel} + \frac{x \cdot Q_{skel} \cdot C_{skel_tis}}{P} - x \cdot Q_{skel} \cdot C_{skel_cap} \\ \frac{dM_{skel_tis}}{dt} &= -\frac{x \cdot Q_{skel} \cdot C_{skel_tis}}{P} + x \cdot Q_{skel} \cdot C_{skel_cap} - V_{skel_tis} \cdot C_{skel} \cdot kskelab - M_{skel_pc} \cdot k_{de} \\ \frac{dM_{skel_pc}}{dt} &= V_{skel_tis} \cdot C_{skel} \cdot kskelab - M_{skel_pc} \cdot k_{de}\end{aligned}$$

Skin

$$\frac{dM_{skin_cap}}{dt} = C_{art} \cdot Q_{skin} - C_{skin_cap} \cdot Q_{skin} + \frac{x \cdot Q_{skin} \cdot C_{skin_tis}}{P_{skin}} - x \cdot Q_{skin} \cdot C_{skin_cap}$$

$$\frac{dM_{skin_tis}}{dt} = -\frac{x \cdot Q_{skin} \cdot C_{skin_tis}}{P_{skin}} + x \cdot Q_{skin} \cdot C_{skin_cap} - V_{skin_tis} \cdot C_{skin} \cdot k_{skinab} - M_{skin_pc} \cdot k_{de}$$

$$\frac{dM_{skin_pc}}{dt} = V_{skin_tis} \cdot C_{skin} \cdot k_{skinab} - M_{skin_pc} \cdot k_{de}$$

Soft tissues

$$\frac{dM_{soft_cap}}{dt} = C_{art} \cdot Q_{soft} - C_{soft_cap} \cdot Q_{soft} + \frac{x \cdot Q_{soft} \cdot C_{soft_tis}}{P_{soft}} - x \cdot Q_{soft} \cdot C_{soft_cap}$$

$$\frac{dM_{soft_tis}}{dt} = -\frac{x \cdot Q_{soft} \cdot C_{soft_tis}}{P_{soft}} + x \cdot Q_{soft} \cdot C_{soft_cap} - V_{soft_tis} \cdot C_{soft} \cdot k_{softab} - M_{soft_pc} \cdot k_{de}$$

$$\frac{dM_{soft_pc}}{dt} = V_{soft_tis} \cdot C_{soft} \cdot k_{softab} - M_{soft_pc} \cdot k_{de}$$

Blood

$$\frac{dArt^{blood}}{dt} = C_{lu_cap} \cdot Q_{lu} - C_{art} \cdot (Q_{li} + Q_{spl} + Q_{ki} + Q_{ht} + Q_{br} + Q_{ut} + Q_{skel} + Q_{skin} + Q_{soft}) - 0.19 \cdot V_{blood} \cdot C_{art} \cdot k_{bloodab} - 0.19 \cdot M_{blood_pc} \cdot k_{de}$$

$$\frac{dVen^{blood}}{dt} = C_{li_cap} \cdot (Q_{li} + Q_{spl}) + C_{ki_cap} \cdot Q_{ki} + C_{ht_cap} \cdot Q_{ht} + C_{br_cap} \cdot Q_{br} + C_{ut_cap} \cdot Q_{ut} + C_{skel_cap} \cdot Q_{skel} + C_{skin_cap} \cdot Q_{skin} + C_{soft_cap} \cdot Q_{soft} - (C_{ven} \cdot Q_{ven}) - 0.81 \cdot V_{blood} \cdot C_{ven} \cdot k_{bloodab} - 0.81 \cdot M_{blood_pc} \cdot k_{de}$$

$$\frac{dM_{blood_pc}}{dt} = (0.81 \cdot V_{blood} \cdot C_{ven} + 0.19 \cdot V_{blood} \cdot C_{art}) \cdot k_{bloodab} - M_{blood_pc} \cdot k_{de}$$

Feces

$$\frac{dM_{feces}}{dt} = CLE_{hep} \cdot M_{li_tis} + CLE_{ua} \cdot M_{ua} + CLE_{muc} \cdot M_{tb}$$

Urine

$$\frac{dM_{urine}}{dt} = CLE_{ur} \cdot M_{ki_cap}$$

Concentrations

$$C_{lu_tis} = M_{lu_tis}/V_{lu_tis}$$

$$C_{lu_cap} = M_{lu_cap}/V_{lu_cap}$$

$$C_{li_tis} = M_{li_tis}/V_{li_tis}$$

$$C_{li_cap} = M_{li_cap}/V_{li_cap}$$

$$C_{spl_tis} = M_{spl_tis}/V_{spl_tis}$$

$$C_{spl_cap} = M_{spl_cap}/V_{spl_cap}$$

$$C_{ki_tis} = M_{ki_tis}/V_{ki_tis}$$

$$C_{ki_cap} = M_{ki_cap}/V_{ki_cap}$$

$$C_{ht_tis} = M_{ht_tis}/V_{ht_tis}$$

$$C_{ht_cap} = M_{ht_cap}/V_{ht_cap}$$

$$C_{br_tis} = M_{br_tis}/V_{br_tis}$$

$$C_{br_cap} = M_{br_cap}/V_{br_cap}$$

$$C_{ut_tis} = M_{ut_tis}/V_{ut_tis}$$

$$C_{ut_cap} = M_{ut_cap}/V_{ut_cap}$$

$$C_{skel_tis} = M_{skel_tis}/V_{skel_tis}$$

$$C_{skel_cap} = M_{skel_cap}/V_{skel_cap}$$

$$C_{skin_tis} = M_{skin_tis}/V_{skin_tis}$$

$$C_{skin_cap} = M_{skin_cap}/V_{skin_cap}$$

$$C_{soft_tis} = M_{soft_tis}/V_{soft_tis}$$

$$C_{soft_cap} = M_{soft_cap}/V_{soft_cap}$$

$$C_{art} = Art_{blood}/(0.19 * V_{blood})$$

$$C_{ven} = Ven_{blood}/(0.81 * V_{blood})$$

Uptake rates by phagocytizing cells

$$kluab = k_{ab0} * \left(1 - \frac{M_{lu_pc}}{Wm_{lu} * uptake_{lu}}\right)$$

$$kliab = k_{ab0} * \left(1 - \frac{M_{li_pc}}{Wm_{li} * uptake_{li}}\right)$$

$$ksplab = k_{ab0_spl} * \left(1 - \frac{M_{spl_pc}}{Wm_{spl} * uptake_{spl}}\right)$$

$$kkiab = k_{ab0} * \left(1 - \frac{M_{ki_pc}}{Wm_{ki} * uptake_{ki}}\right)$$

$$khtab = k_{ab0} * \left(1 - \frac{M_{ht_pc}}{Wm_{ht} * uptake_{ht}}\right)$$

$$kbrab = k_{ab0} * \left(1 - \frac{M_{br_pc}}{Wm_{br} * uptake_{br}}\right)$$

$$kutab = k_{ab0} * \left(1 - \frac{M_{ut_pc}}{Wm_{ut} * uptake_{ut}}\right)$$

$$kskelab = k_{ab0} * \left(1 - \frac{M_{skel_pc}}{Wm_{skel} * uptake_{skel}}\right)$$

$$kskinab = k_{ab0} * \left(1 - \frac{M_{skin_pc}}{Wm_{skin} * uptake_{skin}}\right)$$

$$ksoftab = k_{ab0} * \left(1 - \frac{M_{soft_pc}}{Wm_{soft} * uptake_{soft}}\right)$$

$$kbloodab = k_{ab0} * \left(1 - \frac{M_{blood_pc}}{Wm_{blood} * uptake_{blood}}\right)$$

$$kalab = k_{ab0} * \left(1 - \frac{M_{al_pc}}{Wm_{al} * uptake_{al}}\right)$$

Table A3.1: ODE system parameter description.

Parameter	Units	Description
M_{i_cap}	ug	Mass in capillaries of organ i
M_{i_tis}	ug	Mass in tissue of organ i
M_{i_pc}	ug	Mass in PCs of organ i
k_{ua-br}	h^{-1}	Transfer rate from upper airways to brain
k_{al_pc-tb}	h^{-1}	Transfer rate of inactive PCs from alveolar to tracheobronchial
k_{lu-al}	h^{-1}	Transfer rate from lungs interstitium to alveolar region
k_{al-lu}	h^{-1}	Transfer rate from alveolar region to lungs interstitium
IVR	L/h	Inhalation volume rate
EC	mg/m^3	Exposure concentration
D_{ua}	unitless	Deposition fraction in upper airways
D_{tb}	unitless	Deposition fraction in tracheobronchial region
D_{al}	unitless	Deposition fraction in alveolar region
x_i	unitless	Permeability coefficient between blood and tissue
P_i	unitless	Partition coefficient between tissue and blood
CLE_{ua}	h^{-1}	Clearance rate from upper airways
CLE_{muc}	h^{-1}	Mucociliary clearance rate
CLE_{hep}	h^{-1}	Hepatobiliary clearance rate
CLE_{ur}	h^{-1}	Urinary clearance rate
Q_i	mL/h	Regional blood flow of organ i
C_{i_tis}	ug/mL	Concentration in tissue of organ i
V_{i_tis}	mL	Tissue volume of organ i
C_{i_cap}	ug/mL	Concentration in the capillaries of organ i
V_{i_cap}	mL	Volume of capillaries of organ i
k_{de}	h^{-1}	Desorption rate by PCs
k_{ab0}	h^{-1}	Maximum uptake rate by PCs
Wm_i	ug	PCs weight of organ i
$uptake_i$	ug of NPs/ ug of PCs	Maximum uptake capacity of NPs by PCs of organ i

Annex 5: PBPK group plots

Figure A6.1: Mass-time profiles of the trachea compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours indicate the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.2: Mass-time profiles of the BALF (free alveolar) compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours indicate the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.3: Mass-time profiles of the BALC (alveolar PCs) compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours indicate the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.4: Mass-time profiles of the lavaged lungs compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours match the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.5: Mass-time profiles of the liver compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours indicate the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.6: Mass-time profiles of the spleen compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours indicate the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.7: Mass-time profiles of the kidneys compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours indicate the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.8: Mass-time profiles of the heart compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours indicate the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.9: Mass-time profiles of the brain compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours indicate the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.10: Mass-time profiles of the uterus compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours indicate the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.11: Mass-time profiles of the skeleton compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours indicate the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.12: Mass-time profiles of the skin compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours indicate the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.13: Mass-time profiles of the soft tissues compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours indicate the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.14: Mass-time profiles of the blood compartment. Solid lines represent the PBPK predictions and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). Colours indicate the corresponding rat groups (1: 0h p.e., 2: 4h p.e., 3: 24 h p.e., 4: 4d p.e., 5: 28d p.e.).

Figure A6.15: Mass-time profile of the feces compartment. The solid line represents the PBPK prediction and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). The data and curves correspond to the 5th group; i.e., the rats that were sacrificed at day 28.

Figure A5.16: Mass-time profile of the urine compartment. The solid line represents the PBPK prediction and dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019). The data and curves correspond to the 5th group; i.e., the rats that were sacrificed at day 28.

Annex 6: PBPK VPC plots

Figure A5.1: VPC plot for the trachea compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.2: VPC plot for the BALC (alveolar PCs) compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.3: VPC plot for the BALF (free alveolar) compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.4: VPC plot for the lavaged lungs compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.5: VPC plot for the liver compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.6: VPC plot for the spleen compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.7: VPC plot for the kidneys compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.8: VPC plot for the heart compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.9: VPC plot for the brain compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.10: VPC plot for the uterus compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.11: VPC plot for the skeleton compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.12: VPC plot for the skin compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.13: VPC plot for the soft tissues compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.14: VPC plot for the blood compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.15: VPC plot for the feces compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Figure A6.16: VPC plot for the urine compartment. The line presents the median prediction using the averaged exposure conditions, the dots depict the biodistribution data from Kreyling *et al.* (2019), the pink ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 5th percentile of the simulations, the gray ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 50th percentile of the simulations and the green ribbon corresponds to the 95% PI of the 95th percentile of the simulations.

Annex 7: Phenotypic data for the 232 samples included in the analysis

Table A7.1: ENMs doses range from 0 µg/mouse for control samples, corresponding to a 'negative' dose, to 54 µg/mouse corresponding to a 'middle' dose, 162 µg/mouse corresponding to a 'high' dose, and 486 µg/mouse corresponding to a 'very_high' dose for the animals exposed to ENMs via a single intratracheal instillation.

SampleID	Array	ENM (type, size in nm)	Dose	Dose (µg/mouse)	Time
GSM2157260	set 1	anatase20	negative	0	1d post-exposure
GSM2157261	set 1	anatase20	middle	54	1d post-exposure
GSM2157262	set 1	anatase20	high	162	1d post-exposure
GSM2157263	set 1	anatase20	veryHigh	486	1d post-exposure
GSM2157264	set 1	anatase20	veryHigh	486	28d post-exposure
GSM2157265	set 1	anatase20	negative	0	28d post-exposure
GSM2157266	set 1	anatase20	middle	54	28d post-exposure
GSM2157267	set 1	anatase20	veryHigh	486	1d post-exposure
GSM2157268	set 1	anatase20	high	162	1d post-exposure
GSM2157269	set 1	anatase20	middle	54	1d post-exposure
GSM2157270	set 1	anatase20	negative	0	1d post-exposure
GSM2157271	set 1	anatase20	high	162	28d post-exposure
GSM2157272	set 1	anatase20	negative	0	28d post-exposure
GSM2157273	set 1	anatase20	veryHigh	486	28d post-exposure
GSM2157274	set 1	anatase20	middle	54	28d post-exposure
GSM2157275	set 1	anatase20	negative	0	1d post-exposure
GSM2157276	set 1	anatase20	middle	54	1d post-exposure
GSM2157277	set 1	anatase20	high	162	1d post-exposure
GSM2157278	set 1	anatase20	middle	54	28d post-exposure
GSM2157279	set 1	anatase20	negative	0	28d post-exposure
GSM2157280	set 1	anatase20	veryHigh	486	28d post-exposure
GSM2157281	set 1	anatase20	high	162	28d post-exposure
GSM2157282	set 1	anatase20	negative	0	1d post-exposure
GSM2157283	set 1	anatase20	veryHigh	486	1d post-exposure
GSM2157284	set 1	anatase20	middle	54	1d post-exposure
GSM2157285	set 1	anatase20	high	162	1d post-exposure
GSM2157286	set 1	anatase20	veryHigh	486	28d post-exposure
GSM2157287	set 1	anatase20	high	162	28d post-exposure
GSM2157288	set 1	anatase20	middle	54	28d post-exposure

GSM2157289	set 1	anatase20	negative	0	28d post-exposure
GSM2157290	set 1	anatase20	high	162	1d post-exposure
GSM2157291	set 1	anatase20	middle	54	1d post-exposure
GSM2157292	set 1	anatase20	veryHigh	486	1d post-exposure
GSM2157293	set 1	anatase20	negative	0	28d post-exposure
GSM2157294	set 1	anatase20	high	162	28d post-exposure
GSM2157295	set 1	anatase20	veryHigh	486	28d post-exposure
GSM2157296	set 1	anatase20	middle	54	28d post-exposure